

Self-Made Algebraic Magic, Semi-Magic and Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Orders 3 to 7

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The whole work as pdf files is available at author's sites:

Magic and Semi-Magic Squares:<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=16158>

Pandiagonal Magic Squares:<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=16523>

This work is without use of any kind of programming language

Abstract

*This work brings **magic, semi-magic and pandiagonal** magic squares of orders 3 to 7 for **reduced entries**. By **reduced or less entries**, we understand that instead of normal n^2 entries of a magic square order n , we are using less number of entries. Moreover, in these situations the entries are no more sequential numbers. These **entries** are **non-sequential positive and negative numbers**. Sometimes, we call these kind of magic squares as **self-made**. It means that these are complete in themselves. Just put the values of entries and choose the magic sum, we get a magic square. In some cases, there maybe **decimal or fractional** values of entries depending on the types of magic squares. Different kind of magic squares are used to bring these **self-made** magic squares. These are of type, **block-wise, cornered, single-digit bordered, double-digit bordered, etc**. In some cases, the idea of **magic rectangles** is also applied. In each case, these are considered with **equal width and length**. This work for the orders 3 to 7 brings magic, semi-magic and pandiagonal magic squares. Obviouly, for order 3, we don't have pandiagonal magic squares. This work is available online at the above two links. For similar kind of work for other orders the readers are suggested to see the references [30]-[43].*

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1 Introduction

This work brings **self-made algebraic pandiagonal** magic squares of orders 3 to 7. By **self-made** or **reduced** or **less entries**, we understand that instead of normal n^2 entries of a magic square order n , we are using less numbers of entries, where the magic square is complete in itself. Putting any integer values for these less entries, we shall get always a magic square. Moreover, in these situations the entries are no more **sequential** numbers. These entries are **non-sequential positive** and/or **negative** numbers. In some cases, these may be **decimal** or **fractional** values depending on the way of choosing the entries. Sometime to avoid **decimal** or **fractional** entries we apply certain conditions. These conditions depends on the types of magic squares. The name **self-made** is not known in the literature of magic squares. It is being introduced for first time. The work is based on different types of magic squares, such as, **pandiagonal, block-wise, cornered, single-digit bordered, double-digit bordered**, etc. It is not necessary, but we worked with **magic rectangles** having equal width and length for the same category within a magic square. If we relax this condition, i.e., by considering only equality of width, still we have good results.

This work for the orders 3 to 7 brings **magic, semi-magic** and **pandiagonal** magic squares. Obviously, for order 3, we don't have pandiagonal magic squares. This work is available online at the above two links. The table below give the numbers of **self-made algebraic** magic squares of order 3 to 7. For more details refer author's previous works [30]-[43].

Order	Magic Squares	Semi-Magic Squares	Pandiagonal Magic Squares	Total
3	1	1	0	2
4	2	0	2	4
5	2	1	3	6
6	5	1	6	12
7	5	3	8	16

The author also worked with **self-made** magic squares of orders 8, 9 and 10 studied in [41, 42, 43] respectively. The details are as follows:

Order	Magic Squares	Semi-Magic Squares	Pandiagonal Magic Squares	Total
8	8	5	13	26 [41]
9	10	9	18	28 [42]
10	15	14	29	58 [43]

For order 11, few results given in [34]. Still more results on order 11 are also under study. For order 12, the magic and semi-magic are given in [38, 39]. Still it is left to complete the part with pandiagonal magic squares. It shall be done soon.

The author [30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35] also worked on similar kind of work but from different point of view. This work is for the magic squares of orders 3 to 12 for the **dates** and **days** of the year 2025, where the **dates** are few entries and **days** are the sums of the magic squares.

2 Magic Square of order 3

Example 2.1. A magic square of order 3 is given by

			15
8	1	6	15
3	5	7	15
4	9	2	15
15	15	15	15

2.1 Self-Made Algebraic Magic and Semi-Magic Squares of Order 3

Result 2.1. A magic square of order 3 with *reduced entries algebraic* is given by

$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$
$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	$M/3$	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$
$A1$	$A2$	$M-A1-A2$

• Details

Knowing only two entries $A1$ and $A2$ and the magic sum M , we can construct a magic square of order 3. The some of the entries are **decimal** numbers. To avoid this we may consider the magic sum as **multiple of 3**. The Result 2.1 shall be used frequently in works on reduced magic squares of orders 5, 7 and 9. This magic square can seen in the web-site of F. Gaspalou [3].

Below are two examples. One is with **decimal** entries and another is with magic sums as multiple of 3. These are based on 2.1.

Example 2.2. A magic square of order 3 with reduced entries is given by

	mgc			28
	11	15	2	28
	1/3	9 1/3	18 1/3	28
	16 2/3	3 2/3	7 2/3	28
	28	28	28	28

	mgc			30
	5	16	9	30
	14	10	6	30
	11	4	15	30
	30	30	30	30

The first example is with **decimal** entries because the magic sum is not a multiple of 3. The second example is with integer values as the sum of magic square is a **multiple of 3**.

The magic square of order 3 given in Result 2.1 is with **decimal** entries except the magic sum multiple of 3. To get normal entries, below is another result giving **reduced entries semi-magic** square of order 3

Result 2.2. A **semi-magic** square of order 3 with reduced entries algebraic semi-magic is given by

a1	M-a1-b1	b1
M-a1-a2	a1+a2+b1 +b2-M	M-b1-b2
a2	M-a2-b2	b2

• Details

Knowing only four entries $a1$, $a2$, $b1$ and $b2$ and the magic sum M , we can construct a **semi-magic** square of order 3. This result is applied in construction of magic squares of orders 6, 9 etc.

3 Self-Made Algebraic Magic Squares of order 4

We shall present two different forms of magic squares of order 4 for **reduced entries**. One is a normal and second is **striped** magic squares of order 4.

Result 3.1. *Let's consider the following magic square of order 4*

A1	M+A4-A6-A1	A6-A3-A4	A3
A6	A4	A5	M-A4-A5-A6
A2+A3-A6	A1+A2-A5	M-A1-A2-A4	A4+A5+A6-A2-A3
M-A1-A2-A3	A5-A2-2*A4+A6	A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6	A2

• Details

It is a normal magic square. In this case the entries are always integers independent of magic sum even or odd numbers. The letter S represents the magic sum of order 4. This magic square is due to F. Gaspalou [3]. See the examples below.

Example 3.1. *Let's consider following two examples of reduced entries magic squares of order 4 based on the Result 3.1*

	mgc				70					mgc				101
	11	51	-11	19	70					11	82	-11	19	101
	31	23	27	-11	70					31	23	27	20	101
	3	-1	21	47	70					3	-1	52	47	101
	25	-3	33	15	70					56	-3	33	15	101
4x4	70	70	70	70	70					4x4	101	101	101	101

There are much more way to write **reduced entries** magic squares of order 4. See below

Result 3.2. *Let's consider following magic square of order 4 with different kind of reduced entries*

A1	A2	S-A1-A6-A2	A6
A3	A4	A7	S-A4-A7-A3
A5+A6-A3	A1+A5-A7	S-A1-A5-A4	A4+A7+A3-A5-A6
S-A1-A5-A6	S-A1-A5-A4+A7-A2	2*A1+A5+A6+A4-A7+A2-S	A5

Result 3.3. Let's consider following magic square of order 4 with different kind of reduced entries

A1	A4	A6	S-A1-A4-A6
A2	S-A1-A2-A4	2*A1+A2+A3-A5+A6-S	S-A1-A2-A3+A4+A5-A6
A3	A5	S-A1-A3-A6	A1-A5+A6
S-A1-A2-A3	A1+A2-A5	S-A1-A2+A5-A6	A1+A2+A3+A6-S

Result 3.4. Let's consider following magic square of order 4 with different kind of reduced entries

A1	A3-S+A6	2*S-2*A3-A6-A1	A3
2*S+A4-A3-A6-A1	A4	A5	A3-A5-2*A4-S+A6+A1
A2+2*A3-2*S+A1-A4+A6	A1+A2-A5	S-A1-A2-A4	2*A4+A5+2*S-2*A3-A6-A1-A2
S-A1-A2-A3	A5-A2+2*S-A3-A6-A4-A1	2*A1+A2+2*A3-A5-2*S+A6+A4	A2

In the above three results the letter S represents the magic square of order 4. The readers can try to get some examples based on above three results.

Result 3.5. Let's consider following *striped* magic square of order 4 for reduced entries:

A4-2*A2-A3+2*m-A1	A1	A2	A2+A3-A4
A1-A4+2*A2+A3-m	m-A1	m-A2	A4-A2-A3+m
A3	A4	A1-A4+A2	2*m-A3-A1-A2
m-A3	m-A4	m-A1+A4-A2	A3+A1+A2-m

• Details

The magic square given in Result 3.2 is not a *pandiagonal*. In this case the entries are always integers, while magic sum is always an even numbers. The magic sums of *magic rectangles* may be even or odd. In this case, $S = 2 \times m$, where S is the magic sum of order 4 and m is the width of the magic rectangle of order $m \times 2m$. See below two examples:

Example 3.2. Let's consider two examples of *stripedmagic* squares of order 4 based on the Result 3.2:

4	mgc					66	4	mgc					86
	30	11	14	11	66		50	11	14	11	86		
	3	22	19	22	66		-7	32	29	32	86		
	17	20	5	24	66		17	20	5	44	86		
	16	13	28	9	66		26	23	38	-1	86		
	66	66	66	66	66		86	86	86	86	86		

3.1 Self-Made Algebraic Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order 4

We shall present two different forms of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 for **reduced entries**. One is normal **pandiagonal** magic square while second one is **striped pandiagonal** magic square.

Result 3.6. A *pandiagonal* magic square of order 4 with *reduced entries* is given by

A1	A2	A3	S-A1-A2-A3
A4	S-A1-A2-A4	A1-A3+A4	A2+A3-A4
S/2-A3	A1+A2+A3-S/2	S/2-A1	S/2-A2
S/2-A1+A3-A4	S/2-A2-A3+A4	S/2-A4	A1+A2+A4-S/2

• Details

The magic square given in Result 3.6 is **pandiagonal**. We observe that, in the last two lines of this result the sum S is divided by 2. In order to avoid **decimal** or **fractional** entries, the magic sum should be multiple of 2. This magic square of order 4 is due to F. Gaspalou [3]. See below two examples:

Example 3.3. Let's consider following two examples of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 based on the Result 3.6:

	pan	335	335	335	335			pan	224	224	224	224
335	11	22	40	262	335		224	21	22	44	137	224
335	33	269	4	29	335		224	5	176	-18	61	224
335	127.5	-94.5	156.5	145.5	335		224	68	-25	91	90	224
	163.5	138.5	134.5	-101.5	335			130	51	107	-64	224
4x4	335	335	335	335	335		4x4	224	224	224	224	224

Result 3.7. Let's consider following *striped pandiagonal* magic square of order 4 for reduced entries:

A3+A2-A1	A1	A4-A2	A4-A3
A1-A3-A2+A4	A4-A1	A2	A3
A2	A3	A1-A3-A2+A4	A4-A1
A4-A2	A4-A3	A3+A2-A1	A1

• **Details**

The magic square given in Result 3.7 is *pandiagonal*. In this case the entries are always integers, while magic sum is always an even numbers. While the magic sums of *magic rectangles* may be even or odd. In this case, $S = 2 \times m$, where S is the magic sum of order 4 and m is the width of the magic rectangles of order $m \times 2m$. See below two examples:

Example 3.4. Let's consider following two examples of *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 4 based on the Result 3.7:

	pan	46	46	46	46			pan	62	62	62	62
46	25	11	8	2	46		62	25	11	16	10	62
46	-2	12	15	21	46		62	6	20	15	21	62
46	15	21	-2	12	46		62	15	21	6	20	62
	8	2	25	11	46			16	10	25	11	62
	46	46	46	46	46			62	62	62	62	62

4 Magic Squares of order 5

Example 4.1. Let's consider following three examples of magic square of order 5:

5x5	pan	65	65	65	65	65
65	1	7	13	19	25	65
65	18	24	5	6	12	65
65	10	11	17	23	4	65
65	22	3	9	15	16	65
	14	20	21	2	8	65
	65	65	65	65	65	65

5x5	mgc					65
	16	11	12	23	3	65
	9	13	17	25	1	65
	14	15	10	7	19	65
	5	6	22	8	24	65
	21	20	4	2	18	65
	65	65	65	65	65	65

5x5	mgc					65
	22	25	5	7	6	65
	2	12	17	10	24	65
	3	11	13	15	23	65
	18	16	9	14	8	65
	20	1	21	19	4	65
	65	65	65	65	65	65

The first example is one of the classical example of **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5. The second one is **cornered** magic square and the third example is **single-digit bordered** magic square.

Based on these three examples we shall work on reduced entries magic squares of order 5.

4.1 Self-Made Algebraic Magic Squares of Order 5

Below are three results with examples of **reduced entries algebraic** magic squares of order 5.

Result 4.1. Let's consider following reduced entries magic square of order 5:

$S-A_{14}-A_6-A_9-A_3$	$S-A_4-A_8-A_{13}-A_{10}+3A_6-A_2-A_{12}-A_1$	$A_8+2A_4+A_{13}+2A_{14}+A_9+2A_{10}+A_7-2A_6+A_3+A_2+A_{12}-2S$	A_1	$S-A_{14}-A_4-A_7-A_{10}$
A_2	A_3	$A_{11}+A_{13}-A_{14}-2A_6-A_5+A_1-2A_3+S-A_4-A_7+A_8$	$A_3+2A_6+A_5-A_1+A_{14}+A_7-A_8-A_{11}-A_{13}-A_2$	A_4
$A_3+A_{14}-A_8+A_6-A_{11}+A_9-A_2$	A_5	A_6	$A_8-A_{14}-A_9-A_7-2A_6-A_3+A_2-A_5+A_{11}+S$	A_7
A_8	$A_1-A_3+A_4+A_8+A_{13}+A_{10}-3A_6+A_2-A_5$	$A_5-A_1+A_3+S-A_4-2A_8-A_{13}-A_9-2A_{10}+3A_6-A_2$	A_9	A_{10}
A_{11}	A_{12}	$S-A_{11}-A_{12}-A_{13}-A_{14}$	A_{13}	A_{14}

• **Details**

It is a magic square of order 5 with reduced entries. See below two examples:

Example 4.2. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 5 based on the Result 4.1:

5	mgc					72	5	mgc						61
	-52	-52	227	10	-61	72		-63	-63	249	10	-72	61	61
	13	16	-1	25	19	72		13	16	-12	25	19	61	61
	40	22	25	-43	28	72		40	22	25	-54	28	61	61
	31	43	-73	34	37	72		31	43	-84	34	37	61	61
	40	43	-106	46	49	72		40	43	-117	46	49	61	61
	72	72	72	72	72	72		61	61	61	61	61	61	61

These are magic squares with **even** and **odd** numbers magic sums.

Result 4.2. Let's consider following reduced entries magic square of order 5:

$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*(S-M)/2-A5-A6$	$A5+A6-(S-M)/2$
$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	$M/3$	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	$A5$	$S-M-A5$
$A1$	$A2$	$M-A1-A2$	$A6$	$S-M-A6$
$A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	$A4$	$A1+2*(S-M)-2*A4+A2-2*A5-A6$	$(S-M)/2$	$2*M-S$
$A1+3*(S-M)/2+A2-2*A5-A6-A4$	$S-M-A4$	$2*A4-S+M-A1-A2+2*A5+A6$	$2*M-S$	$(S-M)/2$

• **Details**

It is *cornered* magic square of order 5, where there is a magic square of order 3 at the upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of orders 2×3 are of equal width and length. In order to get magic

square without decimal entries, we must consider magic sum of magic square of order 3 as multiple of 3. See below two examples.

Example 4.3. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 5 based on the Result 4.2:

1a	mgc					110		1b	mgc						131
	4	27	29	35	15	110			3	29	31	62	6	131	
	45	20	-5	19	31	110			49	21	-7	19	49	131	
	11	13	36	21	29	110			11	13	39	21	47	131	
	27	17	31	25	10	110			18	17	67	34	-5	131	
	23	33	19	10	25	110			50	51	1	-5	34	131	
5x5	110	110	110	110	110	110		5x5	131	131	131	131	131	131	131

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} := 60$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := 110$$

Second Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} := 63$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := 151$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} := 50 \times 75$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} := 68 \times 102.$$

4.2 Self-Made Algebraic Semi-Magic Squares of Order 5

In this case, we have only one result for **semi-magic** square of order 5. A condition to bring it a magic square is also studied.

Result 4.3. Let's consider following reduced entries magic square of order 5:

A6	2*M-A9-S+A7	S-M-A7	S-M-A6	A9
2*S-3*M+A9-2*A7+A2+A1-A4	A1+A2-M/3	2*M/3-A2	2*M/3-A1	2*M-S+A4+2*A7-A2-A1-A9
2*A7+S-M-A6-A2-A1	4*M/3-2*A1-A2	M/3	2*A1+A2-2*M/3	A6-2*A7+A2+A1
A4	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	S-M-A4
4*M-2*S-A9	A9+2*S-3*M-A7	A7	A6	S-M-A6

• Details

It is *single-digit bordered magic square* of order 5 embedded with a magic square of order 3. It is *semi-magic square* at one diagonal. If we apply the condition $M = \frac{3}{5} \times S$ then it becomes magic square, where M and S are the magic sums of the magic squares of order 3 and 5, respectively. Below are two examples.

Example 4.4. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 5 based on the Result 4.2:

a	semi						210	b	mgc	M/3=S/5					150
	16	58	13	14	19	120		16	28	43	44	19	150		
	-36	-7	48	49	66	120		24	-7	48	49	36	150		
	25	86	30	-26	5	120		55	86	30	-26	5	150		
	14	11	12	67	16	120		14	11	12	67	46	150		
	101	-28	17	16	14	120		41	32	17	16	44	150		
5x5	120	120	120	120	120	120	5x5	150	150	150	150	150	150		

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} := 90$$

$$S_{Sm_{5 \times 5}} := 120$$

Second Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} := 90$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := 150$$

The first magic square is **semi-magic**. The second one is magic square as it satisfies the condition $M = \frac{3}{5} \times S$.

4.3 Self-Made Algebraic Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order 5

Below are three results with examples on **reduced entries algebraic pandiagonal** magic squares of order 5.

Result 4.4. *Let's consider following reduced entries magic square of order 5:*

A1	A2	S-A1-A2-A3-A4	A3	A4
A9-A2+A8	A6	A1+A2+A3+A4-A6-A7-A8	A7	S-A1-A3-A4-A9
A2+A3+A4-A6-A8	S-A1-A2-A3-A4+A7-A9	A8	A8-A2-A3+A6+A9	A1+A2+A3-A7-A8
A8-A3+A6	A1-A7+A9	A2+A3-A8	S-A1-A6-A8-A9	A8-A2+A7
S-A1-A4-A8-A9	A3+A4-A6	A8-A2-A3+A6+A7	A1+A2-A7	A9

• Details

*It is an **algebraic pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 with reduced entries. The letter M represents the magic sum of order 5. This magic square can be seen in F. Gaspalou [3] web-site. See below two examples.*

Example 4.5. *Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 5 based on the Result 4.4:*

2a	pan	140	140	140	140	140		2b	pan	141	141	141	141	141
140	21	24	38	27	30	140		141	21	24	39	27	30	141
140	57	33	-6	36	20	140		141	57	33	-6	36	21	141
140	9	32	39	63	-3	140		141	9	33	39	63	-3	141
140	45	27	12	5	51	140		141	45	27	12	6	51	141
	8	24	57	9	42	140			9	24	57	9	42	141
5x5	140	140	140	140	140	140		5x5	141	141	141	141	141	141

These are **pandiagonal** magic squares with **even** and **odd** numbers magic sums.

Result 4.5. *Let's consider following reduced entries magic square of order 5:*

A2	M/3-A2+A3	2*M/3-A3	A1	2*M/3-A1
M-A2-A3	M/3	A3+A2-M/3	M/3	M/3
A3	M/3+A2-A3	2*M/3-A2	4*M/3-A1-A3-A2	A1-2*M/3+A3+A2
M-A1-A2	M/3	A1+A3-M/3	A2	(2/3)*M-A3
A1+A2-M/3	M/3	M-A1-A3	A3	(2/3)*M-A2

• Details

It is **cornered pandiagonal** magic square of order 5, where there is a magic square of order 3 at the upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of orders 2×3 are of equal width and length. In order to get it a **pandiagonal** magic square, we applied the condition $S = \frac{5}{3} \times M$, where M and S represents the magic sums of orders 3 and 5 respectively. Doing like this still we have a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5. See below two examples.

Example 4.6. *Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 5 based on the Result 4.5:*

1a	mgc						110		1b	mgc						131
	4	27	29	35	15	110			3	29	31	62	6	131		
	45	20	-5	19	31	110			49	21	-7	19	49	131		
	11	13	36	21	29	110			11	13	39	21	47	131		
	27	17	31	25	10	110			18	17	67	34	-5	131		
	23	33	19	10	25	110			50	51	1	-5	34	131		
5x5	110	110	110	110	110	110		5x5	131	131	131	131	131	131		

These are **pandiagonal** magic squares with **even** and **odd** numbers magic sums.

Result 4.6. *Let's consider following reduced entries magic square of order 5:*

A2	A1-A3+M/3	M/3	M-A1-A2	A3
2*M/3-A2 +A3-A1	2*M/3-A2	A2+A3-M/3	2*M/3-A3	A1-A3+A2
M/3	M/3+A2-A3	M/3	M/3-A2+A3	M/3
A1	A3	M-A2-A3	A2	2*M/3-A1
2*M/3-A3	M/3+A3-A1	M/3	A2+A1-M/3	2*M/3-A2

• Details

It is **single-digit bordered pandiagonal** magic square of order 5, where there is a magic square of order 3 in the middle. In order to get it a **pandiagonal** magic square, we applied the condition $S = \frac{5}{3} \times M$, where M and S represents the magic sums of orders 3 and 5 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 4.7. *Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 5 based on the Result 4.6:*

	pan	60	60	60	60	60			pan	75	75	75	75	75
60	15	4	12	10	19	60		75	15	7	15	19	19	75
60	17	9	22	5	7	60		75	23	15	19	11	7	75
60	12	8	12	16	12	60		75	15	11	15	19	15	75
60	11	19	2	15	13	60		75	11	19	11	15	19	75
	5	20	12	14	9	60			11	23	15	11	15	75
5x5	60	60	60	60	60	60		5x5	75	75	75	75	75	75

These are **pandiagonal** magic squares with **even** and **odd** numbers magic sums. We get even and odd numbers magic sums. It happens as we choose magic square of order 3 multiple of 3 having even and odd magic sums, such as 36 and 45 respectively.

5 Magic Squares of Order 6

Below are four examples of magic squares of order 6. One is normal magic square. The second one is **cornered** and third one is **single-digit bordered** magic squares. While the fourth one is striped magic square. All the three examples are for the **sequential entries** from 1 to 36.

Example 5.1. Let's consider following two magic squares of order 6

6	mgc						111
	1	35	34	33	2	6	111
	30	8	28	9	11	25	111
	24	23	15	16	20	13	111
	18	14	21	22	17	19	111
	7	26	10	27	29	12	111
	31	5	3	4	32	36	111
©IJT	111	111	111	111	111	111	111

6	mgc						111
	17	22	11	24	29	8	111
	12	23	18	21	27	10	111
	26	13	20	15	35	2	111
	19	16	25	14	9	28	111
	4	3	36	30	6	32	111
	33	34	1	7	5	31	111
©IJT	111	111	111	111	111	111	111

6	mgc						111
	6	30	3	36	4	32	111
	35	17	22	11	24	2	111
	29	12	23	18	21	8	111
	27	26	13	20	15	10	111
	9	19	16	25	14	28	111
	5	7	34	1	33	31	111
©IJT	111	111	111	111	111	111	111

6	mgc						111
	11	26	6	31	3	34	111
	28	9	29	8	36	1	111
	10	27	32	5	2	35	111
	25	12	7	30	33	4	111
	21	13	20	19	15	23	111
	16	24	17	18	22	14	111
©IJT	111	111	111	111	111	111	111

The first magic square is a normal, the second one **cornered** and another the third one is **single-digit bordered**.

Remark 1. It is well-known that there are no possibilities of writing *pandiagonal* magic square of order 6 for the *sequential entries*, such as for 1 to 36. Since, we are working with *reduced number of non-sequential entries*, this bring us some results for *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 6.

5.1 Self-Made Algebraic Magic Squares of Order 6

Result 5.1. Let's consider a following magic squares of order 6 with reduced entries:

$A_{19}+A_{20}+A_{21}+A_{22}+A_{23}-A_4-A_7-A_{11}-A_{15}$	A4	A7	A11	A15	$S-A_{19}-A_{20}-A_{21}-A_{22}-A_{23}$
$S-A_{12}-A_5-A_8-A_{16}-A_{19}$	A5	A8	A12	A16	A19
$A_4+A_7+A_{11}+A_{15}-A_{20}-A_{21}-A_{22}-A_{23}-A_1-A_2-A_3+A_5+A_8+A_{12}+A_{16}$	$S-A_4-A_5-A_{12}+A_{21}+A_{22}+A_{23}-A_{17}-A_7-A_8-A_{15}-A_{16}-A_{13}-A_9-A_{11}+A_1+A_2+A_3$	A9	A13	A17	A20
A1	$S+A_{16}+A_{13}+A_6-A_{19}+A_3-A_1-A_{18}-A_{14}-2*A_{21}-A_{22}-A_{23}-A_{20}$	$A_{21}+A_{22}+A_{23}+A_{20}-A_{16}-A_{13}-A_6+A_{19}-A_3$	A14	A18	A21
A2	A6	$S+A_{16}+A_{13}-A_9+A_6-A_{19}+A_3-A_{10}-A_{21}-A_{22}-A_{23}-A_{20}-A_7-A_8$	$A_5+A_{14}+A_{10}+2*A_{21}+A_{22}+3*A_{23}+2*A_{20}-A_4+A_8-A_{15}-A_{16}-A_{13}+2*A_9-2*A_6+2*A_{19}-A_{11}-A_2-A_3-S$	$S-A_{19}-A_{20}-A_{21}-A_{22}-2*A_{23}+A_4+A_7+A_{11}+A_{15}-A_5-A_9-A_{14}$	A22
A3	$A_{12}+A_{18}+A_{14}+A_{21}+A_{20}+A_{17}+A_7+A_8+A_1+5+A_9-2*A_6+A_{19}+A_{11}-A_2-2*A_3-S$	A10	$2*S+A_4-A_8 A_{15}+A_{16}-2*A_9+2*A_6-2*A_{19}+A_2+A_3-A_{12}-A_5-2*A_{14}-A_{10}-2*A_{21}-A_{22}-3*A_{23}-2*A_{20}$	$A_{19}+A_{20}+A_{21}+A_{22}+2*A_{23}-A_4-A_7-A_{11}+A_5+A_9+A_{14}-2*A_{15}-A_{16}-A_{17}-A_{18}$	A23

Details:

It is a normal magic square of order 6. The letter S represent the magic sum of order 6.

Below are two examples based on the Result 5.1.

Example 5.2. Let's consider following two examples:

2a	mgc							150	2b	mgc							175
	78	14	17	21	25	-5	150		78	14	17	21	25	20	175		
	40	15	18	22	26	29	150		65	15	18	22	26	29	175		
	-4	55	19	23	27	30	150		-4	80	19	23	27	30	175		
	11	-21	77	24	28	31	150		11	4	77	24	28	31	175		
	12	16	-1	110	-19	32	150		12	16	24	85	6	32	175		
	13	71	20	-50	63	33	150		13	46	20	0	63	33	175		
	150	150	150	150	150	150	150		175	175	175	175	175	175	175		

Based on **cornered** magic square below is a reduced entries of magic square of order 6.

Result 5.2. Let's consider a following magic squares of order 6 with reduced entries:

A1	M+A4-A6-A1	A6-A3-A4	A3	S-M-A10	A10
A6	A4	A5	M-A4-A5-A6	S-M-A11	A11
A2+A3-A6	A1+A2-A5	M-A1-A2-A4	A4+A5+A6-A2-A3	M-S+A10+A11+A12	2*(S-M)-A10-A11-A12
M-A1-A2-A3	A5-A2-2*A4+A6	A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6	A2	S-M-A12	A12
2*S-3*M+A1-A8+3*A4-A11+A10	S-M-A8	3*M-2*S-A1+2*A8-3*A4+A11-A10+A9	S-M-A9	(S-M)/2	(5*M-3*S)/2
2*M-S-A1+A8-3*A4+A11-A10	A8	3*S-4*M+A1-2*A8+3*A4-A11+A10-A9	A9	(5*M-3*S)/2	(S-M)/2

Details:

It is a **cornered** magic square of order 6 having magic square of order 4 at upper left corner. The two magic rectangles of orders 2×4 are of equal width and length. The letters M and S represents the magic squares of orders 4 and 6 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sums M and S should be of same type, i.e., either **even** or **odd** numbers.

Below are two examples based on the Result 5.2.

Example 5.3. *Let's consider following two examples:*

1a	mgc							140	1b	mgc							151
	21	87	-21	23	0	30	140		21	88	-21	23	10	30	151		
	26	24	25	35	63	-33	140		26	24	25	36	53	-13	151		
	19	18	43	30	-1	31	140		19	18	44	30	9	31	151		
	44	-19	63	22	-2	32	140		45	-19	63	22	8	32	151		
	2	-74	131	1	15	65	140		12	-53	110	11	20	51	151		
	28	104	-101	29	65	15	140		28	93	-70	29	51	20	151		
	140	140	140	140	140	140	140		151	151	151	151	151	151	151		

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} := 110$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 140$$

Second Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} := 111$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 151$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

*

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 4} := 30 \times 60$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 4} := 40 \times 80.$$

Result 5.3. *Let's consider a following magic squares of order 6 with reduced entries:*

A1	M-A1-A2	A2	$4*M-2*A9-A7-2*A8-A10-2*A5-2*A4-A6$	$A5+2*A4+A6+2*A9+A7+2*A8+A10-3*M$	A5
$A1+A2+2*A3+2*A11+A12+A13+2*A14-3*M$	$3*M-2*A11-A12-A13-2*A14-A1-A3$	M-A2-A3	$2*A5+A4+A6+2*A9+A7+2*A8+A10-3*M$	$3*M-2*A9-A7-2*A8-A10-A5-A4$	M-A5-A6
$4*M-2*A11-A12-A13-2*A14-2*A1-A2-2*A3$	$2*A1+A2+A3+2*A11+A12+A13+2*A14-3*M$	A3	A4	M-A4-A6	A6
A7	M-A7-A9	A9	A11	M-A11-A13	A13
M-A7-A8	$A7+A8+A9+A10-M$	M-A9-A10	M-A11-A12	$A11+A12+A13+A14-M$	M-A13-A14
A8	M-A8-A10	A10	A12	M-A12-A14	A14

Details:

It is a magic square of order 6 composed of four equal sums *sem-magic* squares of order 3. In this case, we have $S := 2 \times M$, where S and M are magic sums of order 6 and 3 respectively. See below two examples.

Below are two examples based on the Result 5.3.

Example 5.4. Let's consider following two examples:

	mgc						82			mgc						88
	10	18	13	-138	157	22	82			10	21	13	-126	148	22	88
	199	-170	12	160	-113	-6	82			190	-161	15	151	-104	-3	88
	-168	193	16	19	-3	25	82			-156	184	16	19	0	25	88
	28	-21	34	40	-45	46	82			28	-18	34	40	-42	46	88
	-18	89	-30	-42	137	-54	82			-15	86	-27	-39	134	-51	88
	31	-27	37	43	-51	49	82			31	-24	37	43	-48	49	88
	82	82	82	82	82	82	82			88	88	88	88	88	88	88

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$M_{3 \times 3} := 41(\text{semi - magic})$

$S_{6 \times 6} := 82$

Second Example

$M_{3 \times 3} := 44(\text{semi - magic})$

$S_{6 \times 6} := 88$

Remark 2. Considering *reduced entries algebraic* magic squares of order 3, still we can get *reduced entries algebraic* magic square of order 6, but in this case to avoid **decimal** entries, we must choose the magic sum of order 3 as multiple of 3. By considering semi-magic squares of order 3, we get a magic square of order 6 but without any condition.

Result 5.4. Let's consider a following magic squares of order 6 with reduced entries:

$A1-A6+A7-A12+A13$	A1	$3*m-2*A1-A2-A3-A4+A6-A7+A12-A13$	A2	A3	A4
$m+A6-A7+A12-A13-A1$	m-A1	$2*A1+A2+A3+A4-A6+A7-A12+A13-2*m$	m-A2	m-A3	m-A4
A5	$3*m-A5-A6-A7-A8-A9$	A6	A7	A8	A9
m-A5	$A5+A6+A7+A8+A9-2*m$	m-A6	m-A7	m-A8	m-A9
$A4+A7-A6+A10-A3$	A10	$3*m-A4-A7+A6-2*A10+A3-A11-A12-A13$	A11	A12	A13
$m-A4-A7+A6-A10+A3$	m-A10	$A4+A7-A6+2*A10-A3+A11+A12+A13-2*m$	m-A11	m-A12	m-A13

Details:

It is a magic square of order 6 composed of four equal sums **semi-magic** squares of order 3. Since the magic sums of order 6 is depending on the magic sum of order 3, then in this case the magic sum of order 6 is always an even numbers. In this case, we have $S := 3 \times m$, where m is the width of the magic rectangle $m \times 3m$. See below two examples.

Below are two examples based on the Result 5.4.

Example 5.5. Let's consider following two examples:

	mgc						126			mgc							93
	11	21	22	23	24	25	126			-22	21	22	23	24	25		93
	31	21	20	19	18	17	126			53	10	9	8	7	6		93
	26	27	28	17	-1	29	126			26	27	28	-16	-1	29		93
	16	15	14	25	43	13	126			5	4	3	47	32	2		93
	20	30	-20	31	32	33	126			-13	30	-20	31	32	33		93
	22	12	62	11	10	9	126			44	1	51	0	-1	-2		93
	126	126	126	126	126	126	126			93	93	93	93	93	93		93

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 126$$

Second Example

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 93$$

The width of magic rectangles are 42 and 31 respectively.

Result 5.5. *Let's consider a following magic squares of order 6 with reduced entries:*

A1	m-A1	A6	A7	A8	2*m-A6-A7-A8
A2	m-A2	m-A6	m-A7	m-A8	m-2*m +A6+A7+A8
A3	m-A3	A9-A6-A7-2*A8 +A1+A2+A3+A4 +2*A5-m	A9	A6+A7+2*A8-2*A9 A1-A10-A2-A3-A4- 2*A5+3*m	A10
A4	m-A4	A6+A7+2*A8-A1- A2-A3-A4- 2*A5+2*m-A9	m-A9	2*A9+A1+A10+A2 +A3+A4+2*A5- 2*m-A6-A7-2*A8	m-A10
3*m-A1-A2- A3-A4-A5	A1+A2+A3+ A4+A5-2*m	A11	m-A11+2*A1-A6- A7-2*A8+A3 +A4+2*A5-2*A12	m+A6+A7+2*A8- A3-A4-2*A5+A12- 2*A1	A12
A5	m-A5	m-A11	A11-2*A1+A6+ A7+2*A8-A3-A4- 2*A5+2*A12	2*A1-A6-A7-2*A8 +A3+A4+2*A5- A12	m-A12

Details:

It is a **striped** magic square of order 6 composed two types of stripes: one of type 2×6 and another three of type 2×4 . In this case, we have $S := 3 \times m$, where m is the width of the **strips**. See below two examples.

Below are two examples based on the Result 5.5.

Example 5.6. *Let's consider following two examples:*

	mgc	96	-18	276	48	18	84			mgc	108	-15	285	54	33	93
	11	17	26	29	32	-31	84			11	20	26	29	32	-25	93
	14	14	2	-1	-4	59	84			14	17	5	2	-1	56	93
	17	11	-4	35	-13	38	84			17	14	-7	35	-4	38	93
	20	8	32	-7	41	-10	84			20	11	38	-4	35	-7	93
	-1	29	41	-115	86	44	84			8	23	41	-112	89	44	93
	23	5	-13	143	-58	-16	84			23	8	-10	143	-58	-13	93
	84	84	84	84	84	84	84			93	93	93	93	93	93	93

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

			26	29	32	-31	56				26	29	32	-25	62
11	17	28	2	-1	-4	59	56	11	20	31	5	2	-1	56	62
14	14	28	28	28	28	28		14	17	31	31	31	31	31	
17	11	28	-4	35	-13	38	56	17	14	31	-7	35	-4	38	62
20	8	28	32	-7	41	-10	56	20	11	31	38	-4	35	-7	62
-1	29	28	28	28	28	28		8	23	31	31	31	31	31	
23	5	28	41	-115	86	44	56	23	8	31	41	-112	89	44	62
84	84		-13	143	-58	-16	56	93	93		-10	143	-58	-13	62
			28	28	28	28					31	31	31	31	

5.2 Self-Made Algebraic Semi-Magic Squares of Order 6

Below is a result for **reduced entries semi-magic** squares based on Example ??.

Result 5.6. *Let's consider following semi-magic square of order 6 with reduced entries:*

$4*A_{15}-6*A_7+A_{12}$	$A_{15}+2*A_{13}+2*A_{14}-4*A_{12}-A_7$	$2*A_{12}+9*A_7-6*A_{15}-A_{13}-A_{14}$	$A_{15}-A_{13}-A_7$	$A_{15}-A_{14}-A_7$	A_{12}
$4*A_7-3*A_{15}+A_9+A_{10}+A_{11}$	A_1	$A_4+A_7-A_6-A_1$	$A_6-A_3-A_4$	A_3	$4*A_{15}-A_9-A_{10}-A_{11}-5*A_7$
$A_{15}-A_9-A_7$	A_6	A_4	A_5	$A_7-A_4-A_5-A_6$	A_9
$A_{15}-A_{10}-A_7$	$A_2+A_3-A_6$	$A_1+A_2-A_5$	$A_7-A_1-A_2-A_4$	$A_4+A_5+A_6-A_2-A_3$	A_{10}
$A_{15}-A_{11}-A_7$	$A_7-A_1-A_2-A_3$	$A_5-A_2-2*A_4+A_6$	$A_1+A_2+A_3+2*A_4-A_5-A_6$	A_2	A_{11}
$5*A_7-A_{12}-3*A_{15}$	$4*A_{12}-2*A_{13}-2*A_{14}$	$7*A_{15}+A_{13}+A_1-4-2*A_{12}-10*A_7$	A_{13}	A_{14}	$5*A_7-A_{12}-3*A_{15}$

Details:

It is a **single-digit bordered semi-magic** square of order 6 embedded magic square of orders 4. It is **semi-magic** only at one diagonal. In order to bring it as a magic square we need the following condition:

$$M = \frac{2}{3} \times S, \tag{1}$$

where M and S are magic sums of magic squares of orders 4 and 6 respectively.

Below are two examples based on the Result 5.6. First example is of **semi-magic** squares and the second example as a magic square obtained by applying the conditions given in (1)

Example 5.7. Let's consider a following *semi-magic* square based on the Result 5.6:

s1	semi	M=2*S/3					180
	24	68	21	3	0	44	160
	74	11	93	-11	17	-24	160
	15	26	20	23	41	35	160
	12	5	2	65	38	38	160
	9	68	-5	33	14	41	160
	26	-18	29	47	50	26	160
	160	160	160	160	160	160	160

The **magic** and **semi-magic** sums of above magic square are $M_{4 \times 4} := 110$ and $S_{SM_{6 \times 6}} := 160$.

Example 5.8. Let's consider a following *magic* square with *even* number magic sum based on the Result 5.6:

s2	mgc	M=2*S/3					150
	44	68	-9	3	0	44	150
	64	11	83	-11	17	-14	150
	15	26	20	23	31	35	150
	12	5	2	55	38	38	150
	9	58	-5	33	14	41	150
	6	-18	59	47	50	6	150
	150	150	150	150	150	150	150

The **magic** sums of above magic square are $M_{4 \times 4} := 100$ and $S_{6 \times 6} := 150$. It is a magic square as it satisfies the conditions given in (1), i.e., $M = \frac{2}{3} \times S$.

5.3 Self-Made Algebraic Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order 6

Below are four results with examples on **reduced entries pandiagonal** magic squares of order 6.

Result 5.7. Let's consider a following *magic* square of order 6 with *reduced entries*:

S-A1-A2-A3-A4-A5	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5
A6	A7	A8	$S-2*A4-A12-A11-2*A3-2*A5-A2+A6+2*A7-A13+2*A16-A1+A9$	$2*S/3-A15-A7-A16$	$A15-2*S/3+2*A4-A8+A12-2*A6-A16+A11+2*A3+2*A5+A2-2*A7+A13+A1-A9$
A9	$5*S/6+A5+A3+A4-A8-A6-2*A7-A10-A16-A9$	A10	A11	$A15+A11+3*A3+3*A4+4*A5+A2-A14-A8+2*A12-2*A6-3*A7-A10+2*A13-3*A16+2*A1-2*A9-5*S/6$	$S-A15-2*A11-4*A3-4*A4-5*A5-A2+A14+2*A8-2*A12+3*A6+5*A7+A10-2*A13+4*A16-2*A1+2*A9$
$A11-S/3+2*A5+A2+A13+A3+A4-A14-A6-A7-A16+A1-A9$	A12	A13	$A7+A16-A11+A14+A6-A13+A9-A3-A5$	$2*S/3-A4-A12-A1$	$2*S/3-A5-A2-A13$
A14	A15	$4*S/3-A15-3*A5-2*A13-3*A4+A8-2*A12+2*A6+3*A7-A11-2*A3-A2+2*A16-A1+A9$	$A11+2*A3+2*A4+2*A5+A2-A14+A12-2*A6-2*A7+A13-2*A16+A1-A9-S/3$	A16	$A4+A5-A8+A12-A7+A13-A16$
$S/3-A11-A5-A13+A7+A16$	$S/6+A8-A12+A6+A7+A10+A16-A1+A9-A15-A5-A3-A4$	$A15-S/3+3*A5+3*A4-2*A8+2*A12-2*A6-3*A7+A11+2*A3-A10+A13-2*A16+A1-A9$	$S/3+A5+A13-A7-A16-A9$	$S/2-A2-3*A3-3*A4+A14+A8-A12+A10+3*A16-A1-4*A5+2*A6+4*A7-2*A13+2*A9-A11$	$A11+2*A3+A4+2*A5+A2-A14-A6-2*A7-A10+A13-2*A16+A1-A9$

• **Details**

It is an **algebraic pandiagonal** magic square of order 6 for reduced entries. The letter *S* represents the magic sum. In this case the entries are **non sequential**. We observe that the magic sum is divided by 2, 3 and 6. The represents that the magic sum should be multiple of 6 otherwise, some of the entries may be either **decimal** or **fractional** numbers. See below two examples:

Example 5.9. Let's consider following two examples representing **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 6

	pan	90	90	90	90	90	90			pan	102	102	102	102	102	102
90	-15	15	18	21	24	27	90		102	-3	15	18	21	24	27	102
90	30	33	36	24	-90	57	90		102	30	33	36	36	-82	49	102
90	39	-126	42	45	-33	123	90		102	39	-116	42	45	-43	135	102
90	-18	48	51	72	-27	-36	90		102	-22	48	51	72	-19	-28	102
90	54	57	-54	-48	60	21	90		102	54	57	-38	-52	60	21	102
	0	63	-3	-24	156	-102	90			4	65	-7	-20	162	-102	102
	90	90	90	90	90	90	90			102	102	102	102	102	102	102

In Result 5.9, we observe that the magic sum should be multiple of 6, otherwise we may have **decimal** or **fractional** numbers entries. This is the reason both the examples are with even number magic sums.

Result 5.8. Let's consider a following magic square of order 6 with reduced entries:

$2*M/3-A6$	$A6+A7-M/3$	$2*M/3-A7$	$2*M/3-A2$	$A2+A3-M/3$	$2*M/3-A3$
$A6+A8-M/3$	$M+A1-A6-A7-A8$	$M/3+A7-A1$	$A2+A4-M/3$	$5*M/3-A3-A2-A4-A5$	$A3+A5-M/3$
$2*M/3-A8$	$M/3+A8-A1$	$A1$	$2*M/3-A4$	$A4+A5-M/3$	$2*M/3-A5$
$A2$	$M-A2-A3$	$A3$	$A6$	$M-A6-A7$	$A7$
$M-A2-A4$	$A2+A3+A4+A5-M$	$M-A3-A5$	$M-A6-A8$	$A6+A7+A8-A1-M/3$	$M/3-A7+A1$
$A4$	$M-A4-A5$	$A5$	$A8$	$M/3-A8+A1$	$2*M/3-A1$

• **Details**

It is an **algebraic pandiagonal** magic square of order 6 with four equal sums **semi-magic** squares of order 3. The letter M represent the **semi-magic** sum of order 3, and $S = 2 \times M$ is the magic sum of order S. In order to get **non-decimal** entries, the magic sum of order 3 should be multiple of 3. See below two examples:

Example 5.10. Let's consider following two examples representing **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 6

	pan	96	96	96	96	96	96			pan	90	90	90	90	90	90
96	6	39	3	18	15	15	96		90	4	40	1	16	16	13	90
96	42	-28	34	18	6	24	96		90	43	-31	33	19	1	25	90
96	0	37	11	12	27	9	96		90	-2	36	11	10	28	7	90
96	14	17	17	26	-7	29	96		90	14	14	17	26	-10	29	90
96	14	26	8	-10	60	-2	96		90	11	29	5	-13	61	-3	90
	20	5	23	32	-5	21	96			20	2	23	32	-6	19	90
	96	96	96	96	96	96	96			90	90	90	90	90	90	90

In Result 5.10, we observe that the **semi-magic** of order 3 should be multiple of 3, otherwise we may have **decimal** or **fractional** numbers entries. This is the reason both the examples are with even number magic sums. Any way the **semi-magic** of order 3 are 48 and 45 respectively.

Result 5.9. Let's consider a following magic square of order 6 with reduced entries:

A1	$2*M-A3-A1-A5-A2-A4$	$A3-2*M+2*A5+A2+2*A4+A1$	$M-A5-A4-A1$	$(7/4)*M-2*A5-2*A2-A4+A1$	$2*A5+2*A2+A4-A1-(5/4)*M$
A3	$M-A5-A2-A4$	A2	$A5+A4-A3$	$A2-A1+A6$	$(1/2)*M-A2+A1-A6$
$A2+(1/2)*M-A1-A3$	$A1+A5+A4-(1/2)*M$	$(1/2)*M-A1$	$A3+(1/2)*M-A4+A1-A5-A2$	$(1/2)*M-A6$	A6
$(1/2)*M-A2$	$2*A2+A5+A4-(3/2)*M+A3$	$(5/2)*M-A3-2*A5-2*A2-2*A4$	$A5+A2+A4-(1/2)*M$	$2*A5+A2+A4-(5/4)*M$	$(7/4)*M-2*A5-A2-A4$
$(1/2)*M-A4$	$A4+A1-A6+A5-(1/4)*M$	$(1/4)*M+A6-A1$	$(1/2)*M-A5$	$(1/4)*M$	$(1/4)*M$
A4	$(3/4)*M+A6-A5-A4-A1$	$(1/4)*M+A1-A6$	A5	$(1/4)*M$	$(1/4)*M$

• Details

It is an *algebraic pandiagonal cornered* magic square of order 6, where *pandiagonal* magic square of order 4 is at the upper-left corner. The *magic rectangles* of order 2×4 are of equal width and length. The letter M represents the magic sum of order 4 and $S = \frac{3}{2} \times M$ is the magic sums of order 6. Moreover, both the magic squares of orders 4 and 6 are *pandiagonal*. Moreover, in order avoid decimal or fractional entries, we have magic sum of order 4 as multiple of 4. See below two examples:

Example 5.11. Let's consider following two examples representing *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 6

	pan	66	66	66	66	66	66			pan	72	72	72	72	72	72
66	13	21	11	-1	19	3	66		72	14	21	11	2	19	5	72
66	13	-3	15	19	21	1	66		72	13	0	16	19	21	3	72
66	11	23	9	1	3	19	66		72	13	22	10	3	5	19	72
66	7	3	9	25	1	21	66		72	8	5	11	24	3	21	72
66	5	15	17	7	11	11	66		72	7	15	17	9	12	12	72
	17	7	5	15	11	11	66			17	9	7	15	12	12	72
	66	66	66	66	66	66	66			72	72	72	72	72	72	72

In this case the magic sums of order 6 are 66 and 72 respectively. The magic sums of order 4 are 44 and 48. As written above, we have the magic sums of order as multiple of 4.

Result 5.10. Let's consider a following magic square of order 6 with reduced entries:

$(12/5)*m-A2-2*A1-A4$	A1	$(3/5)*m$	A2	$A4+A1-A3$	A3
$2*A1-(7/5)*m+A4+A2$	m-A1	$(2/5)*m$	m-A2	$m+A3-A4-A1$	m-A3
$(9/10)*m-A1$	$(3/2)*m-A4-A2$	$A4+A2+A1-(9/10)*m$	$(3/2)*m-A4-A1$	$2*A4-A3+A2-(3/2)*m+2*A1$	$(3/2)*m-A4-A2+A3-A1$
$(1/10)*m+A1$	$A4+A2-(1/2)*m$	$(19/10)*m-A4-A2-A1$	$A4+A1-(1/2)*m$	$(5/2)*m-2*A4-A2-2*A1+A3$	$A4+A2-A3+A1-(1/2)*m$
$(12/5)*m+A3-2*A4-A2-2*A1$	$A4+A1-A3$	$(3/5)*m-A4+A3$	$A4+A2-A3$	A1	A4
$2*A4+A2+2*A1-A3-(7/5)*m$	$m+A3-A4-A1$	$A4+(2/5)*m-A3$	$m-A4-A2+A3$	m-A1	m-A4

• Details

It is an *algebraic pandiagonal* magic square of order 6 for reduced entries. It is constructed based three equal sums *magic rectangles* or *strips* of order 2×6 . The letter m represents width of each magic rectangle. The magic sum of order 6 is $S = 3 \times m$. In order to avoid *decimal* or *fractional* entries, the magic sum of width of *magic rectangle* should be multiple of 10. See below two examples:

Example 5.12. Let's consider following two examples representing *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 6

	pan	120	120	120	120	120	120			pan	60	60	60	60	60	60
120	40	10	24	15	13	18	120		60	-12	12	12	15	15	18	60
120	0	30	16	25	27	22	120		60	32	8	8	5	5	2	60
120	26	24	10	29	-1	32	120		60	6	-6	30	-3	33	0	60
120	14	16	30	11	41	8	120		60	14	26	-10	23	-13	20	60
120	37	13	21	18	10	21	120		60	-15	15	9	18	12	21	60
	3	27	19	22	30	19	120			35	5	11	2	8	-1	60
	120	120	120	120	120	120	120			60	60	60	60	60	60	60

Result 5.11. Let's consider a following magic squares of order 6 with reduced entries:

A1	m-A1	A5	A6	A4+m-A7+A1-A5-A6	m-A4+A7-A1
A2	m-A2	m-A5	m-A6	A7-A1+A5+A6-A4	A4-A7+A1
A3	m-A3	A5+A2+A3-m	(1/2)*m-A7+A1	(1/2)*m+A4-A5	2*m+A7-A2-A3-A4-A1
(3/2)*m-A7-A6	A7+A6-(1/2)*m	2*m-A2-A3-A5	(1/2)*m+A7-A1	(1/2)*m-A4+A5	A2+A3-m+A4+A1-A7
(3/2)*m-A1-A2-A3+A7+A6-A4	A1+A2+A3-(1/2)*m-A7-A6+A4	m-A4+A5-A1	A4+A1-A7+A3-(1/2)*m	(3/2)*m-A5-A3	A7
A4	m-A4	A4-A5+A1	(3/2)*m-A4-A1+A7-A3	A5-(1/2)*m+A3	m-A7

Details:

It is a **striped pandiagonal** magic square of order 6 composed two types of stripes: one of type 2×6 and another three of type 2×4 . In this case, we have $S := 3 \times m$, where m is the width of the **strips**. In order to avoid **decimal** entries the value of m should be multiple of 2. See below two examples.

Below are two examples based on the Result 5.11.

Example 5.13. Let's consider following two examples:

	pan	102	102	102	102	102	102			pan	114	114	114	114	114	114
102	10	24	22	25	-12	33	102		114	10	28	22	25	-8	37	114
102	13	21	12	9	46	1	102		114	13	25	16	13	46	1	114
102	16	18	17	-1	14	38	102		114	16	22	13	1	16	46	114
102	-2	36	17	35	20	-4	102		114	4	34	25	37	22	-8	114
102	46	-12	27	0	13	28	102		114	52	-14	31	-2	19	28	114
	19	15	7	34	21	6	102			19	19	7	40	19	10	114
	102	102	102	102	102	102	102			114	114	114	114	114	114	114

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

			22	25	-12	33	68				22	25	-8	37	76	
10	24	34	12	9	46	1	68		10	28	38	16	13	46	1	76
13	21	34	34	34	34	34			13	25	38	38	38	38	38	
16	18	34	17	-1	14	38	68		16	22	38	13	1	16	46	76
-2	36	34	17	35	20	-4	68		4	34	38	25	37	22	-8	76
46	-12	34	34	34	34	34			52	-14	38	38	38	38	38	
19	15	34	27	0	13	28	68		19	19	38	31	-2	19	28	76
102	102		7	34	21	6	68		114	114		7	40	19	10	76
			34	34	34	34						38	38	38	38	

Result 5.12. Let's consider a following magic square of order 6 with reduced entries:

$(1/4)*M$	$(7/2)*M-2*A3-2*A4-2*A5-4*A1-2*A2$	$A3+A4+A5+2*A1+A2-(3/2)*M$	$A4+A1-(1/4)*M$	$A3+A5+A1+A2-(3/4)*M$	$(1/4)*M$
$3*A1+2*A3+2*A4+2*A5+2*A2-(11/4)*M$	A1	A2	$(11/4)*M-3*A1-A3-2*A4-A5-2*A2$	$2*A1+A2+A3+2*A4+A5-(7/4)*M$	$(13/4)*M-3*A1-2*A3-2*A4-2*A5-2*A2$
$(11/4)*M-3*A1-A4-A5-2*A3-2*A2$	A3	$M-A1-A2-A3$	$4*A1-(11/4)*M+2*A3+2*A4+A5+2*A2$	$(11/4)*M-3*A1-2*A3-2*A4-A5-A2$	$3*A1+A4+A5+2*A3+2*A2-(9/4)*M$
$(1/2)*M-A4$	$3*A1+A3+2*A4+A5+2*A2-(9/4)*M$	$(9/4)*M-A3-2*A4-A5-2*A1-A2$	$M/2-A1$	$M/2-A2$	A4
$(1/2)*M-A5$	$(13/4)*M-4*A1-2*A3-2*A4-A5-2*A2$	$A2+3*A1+2*A3+2*A4+A5-(9/4)*M$	$M/2-A3$	$A1+A2+A3-M/2$	A5
$(1/4)*M$	$2*A3+2*A4+2*A5+4*A1+2*A2-3*M$	$2*M-A3-A4-A5-2*A1-A2$	$(3/4)*M-A4-A1$	$(5/4)*M-A3-A5-A1-A2$	$(1/4)*M$

• **Details**

It is an algebraic pandiagonal single-digit bordered magic square of order 6, where the inner is also a pandiagonal magic square of 4. In this case also to avoid decimal or fractional entries we must as magic square of order 4 as multiple of order 4. The letter M represents the magic sum of order 4 and $S = \frac{3}{2} \times M$ is the magic sums of order 6. See below two examples

Example 5.14. Let's consider following two examples representing *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 6

	pan	72	72	72	72	72	72			pan	78	78	78	78	78	78	
72	12	16	4	13	15	12	72		78	13	30	-2	12	12	13	78	
72	9	11	12	19	6	15	72		78	-2	11	12	30	-1	28	78	
72	20	13	12	5	18	4	72		78	31	13	16	-6	29	-5	78	
72	10	5	18	13	12	14	72		78	12	-4	27	15	14	14	78	
72	9	19	6	11	12	15	72		78	11	32	-3	13	10	15	78	
	12	8	20	11	9	12	72			13	-4	28	14	14	13	78	
	72	72	72	72	72	72	72			78	78	78	78	78	78	78	

In this case the magic sums of order 6 are 72 and 78 respectively. The magic sums of order 4 are 48 and 54. As written above, we have the magic sums of order as multiple of 4.

6 Magic Squares of Order 7

Example 6.1. Let's consider following four examples of magic squares of order 7:

1	pan	175		2	mgc							175						
175	1	9	17	25	33	41	49	175			42	38	40	5	4	2	44	175
175	40	48	7	8	16	24	32	175			1	34	37	17	19	18	49	175
175	23	31	39	47	6	14	15	175			3	14	24	29	22	36	47	175
175	13	21	22	30	38	46	5	175			43	15	23	25	27	35	7	175
175	45	4	12	20	28	29	37	175			41	30	28	21	26	20	9	175
175	35	36	44	3	11	19	27	175			39	32	13	33	31	16	11	175
	18	26	34	42	43	2	10	175			6	12	10	45	46	48	8	175
	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175			175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175

3	mgc							175		4	mgc							175
	4	30	44	32	15	13	37	175			26	21	28	30	20	8	42	175
	46	20	6	18	35	9	41	175			27	25	23	33	17	12	38	175
	34	16	26	21	28	17	33	175			22	29	24	14	36	48	2	175
	42	8	27	25	23	47	3	175			34	32	31	13	15	45	5	175
	43	7	22	29	24	39	11	175			16	18	19	35	37	10	40	175
	1	49	48	12	19	36	10	175			46	49	7	47	6	11	9	175
	5	45	2	38	31	14	40	175			4	1	43	3	44	41	39	175
	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175			175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175

The first example is a **pandiagonal** magic square. The second magic square is **single-digit bordered** magic square embedded with magic squares of orders 5 and 3. The third example is **double-digit bordered** magic square with magic square of order 3 in its inner part. In this case the four magic rectangles of order 2×3 are of equal sums. The fourth example is **cornered** magic square having magic squares of orders 3 and 5 at upper-left corner. In this case the each two magic rectangles of order 2×3 and 2×5 are of equal sums.

Based on examples 2, 3 and 4, we shall work with **reduced entries algebraic** magic squares. It is divided in two parts. One when we always have magic squares. The second part is when the results are **semi-magic** squares. In this case, apply conditions to get magic squares.

6.1 Self-Made Algebraic Magic Squares of Order 7

Based on the four examples given in 6.3 we shall bring five different ways to write **reduced entries algebraic** magic squares of order 7. The algebraic structure of these magic square is also presented.

Result 6.1. *Let's consider following reduced entries algebraic magic square of order 7:*

$T+A16+A30+A12-A24+A26-A20-A19-A23+A8-A22-A5-A4-A3-A2-A1-A21$	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	$A24-A26+A20+A19+A23-A8+A22+A21-A16-A30-A12$
A6	A7	$A19+A20+A21+A22+A23+A24-A27-A31-A2-A10-A15$	$A24+A28+A27+A25+A20+A19+A29+A23-A8-A7+A5+A4+A2+A1-A34-3*A16-A32-A30-A12-A11-A10$	$T+A34+3*A16+A15+A32+A31+A30+A12+A11+2*A10-2*A24-A28-A25-2*A20-2*A19-A29-2*A23-A9-A6-A22-A5-A4-A1-A21$	A8	A9
$A24-A26-A25+A20+A23-A8-A6+A22+A5+A4+A3+A2+A1+A21-A16-A14-2*A30-A12$	$A18-A16+A14+A33+A30-A13-A12-A11-2*A10+A25+A19+A23+A8-A7+A6-A22+A5-A34$	A10	A11	A12	$T+A34-A18+2*A16-A33+A30+A12+A10-A24+A26-A20-A19-2*A23+A7-2*A5-A4-A3-A2-A1-A21$	A13
A14	$A34-A18-A17-2*A16-A15-A14-A30+A13-A12+2*A24-A26+A20+A19+A29+A23+A9-A8+A22+A21$	A15	A16	A17	A18	$T-A34+A16+A30-A13+A12-2*A24+A26-A20-A19-A29-A23-A9+A8-A22-A21$
A19	A20	$T-A19-A20-A21-A22-A23-A24$	A21	A22	A23	A24
A25	A26	A27	$T+A34+2*A16+A30+A12+A10-A24-A28-A27-A25-A20-A19-A29-A23+A8+A7-A5-A4-A3-A2-A1-A21$	A28	$A24-A26+A20+A19+A23-A8-A7+A5+A4+A3+A2+A1+A21-A34-2*A16-A30-A12-A10$	A29
A30	$T+A17+3*A16+A15-A33-A9+2*A12+A11+2*A10-2*A24-A25-2*A20-2*A19-A29-2*A23-A6-A5-A1-A21$	A31	A32	$2*A24+A25+2*A20+2*A19+A29+2*A23+A9+A6+A5+A1+A21-A34-A17-3*A16-A15-A32-A31-A30-2*A12-A11-2*A10$	A33	A34

• Details

It is a magic square of order 7. It don't have any condition for integer value entries. We can consider any natural number to bring a magic squares without decimal or fractional entries. The letter T represents the magic sum of order 7. See below two examples.

Example 6.2. *Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 7 based on the Result 6.2:*

	mgc							116										111
	-82	10	13	16	19	22	118	116										111
	25	28	139	52	-193	31	34	116										111
	-119	145	37	40	43	-76	46	116										111
	49	205	52	55	58	61	-364	116										111
	64	67	-313	70	73	76	79	116										111
	82	85	88	-220	91	-104	94	116										111
	97	-424	100	103	25	106	109	116										111
	116	116	116	116	116	116	116	116										111

The magic sums of above two examples are 116 and 111 respectively.

Result 6.2. *Let's consider following reduced entries algebraic magic square of order 7:*

$(T-M)/2-A12$	A14	$A10+A11-(T-M)/4$	$(T-M)/2-A10$	$(T-M)/2-A11$	A9	$(5*M-T)/4+A12-A14-A9$
A13	A12	$3*(T-M)/4-A10-A11$	A10	A11	$(3*T-7*M)/4-A12+A14+A9$	$(5*M-T)/2-A13-A14-A9$
$A15+A16-(T-M)/4$	$3*(T-M)/4-A15-A16$	$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*(T-M)/4-A7-A8$	$A7+A8-(T-M)/4$
$(T-M)/2-A15$	A15	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	A7	$(T-M)/2-A7$
$(T-M)/2-A16$	A16	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	A8	$(T-M)/2-A8$
$A14-A6+A9$	$(3*T-7*M)/4-A12+A13+A14-A6+A9$	$3*(T-M)/4-A4-A5$	A4	A5	$(5*M-T)/2+A12-2*A14-2*A9-A13+A6$	A6
$(5*M-T)/4+A12-A13-A14+A6-A9$	$(5*M-T)/2-2*A14+A6-A9-A13$	$A4+A5-(T-M)/4$	$(T-M)/2-A4$	$(T-M)/2-A5$	$A14+A13-A6$	$T-3*M-A12+2*A14+2*A9+A13-A6$

• Details

It is **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 7 embedded with magic square of order 3. The four magic rectangles of order 2×3 are of equal sums, i.e., equal width and equal length. The magic square of order 3 is with decimal entries. To get the result without decimal entries, we must consider magic sum for order 3 as multiple of 3. The letters M and T are magic sums of magic squares of orders 3 and 7 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 6.3. *Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 7 based on the Result 6.2:*

1a	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT						170	1b	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT						181
	18	24	21	20	19	19	49	170		22	24	19	24	23	19	50	181
	23	22	19	20	21	-9	74	170		23	22	25	20	21	-6	76	181
	31	9	-7	48	49	25	15	170		29	15	-8	50	51	31	13	181
	15	25	86	30	-26	17	23	170		19	25	90	31	-28	17	27	181
	14	26	11	12	67	18	22	170		18	26	11	12	70	18	26	181
	27	-2	31	14	15	69	16	170		27	1	37	14	15	71	16	181
	42	66	9	26	25	31	-29	170		43	68	7	30	29	31	-27	181
	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170		181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} := 90$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} := 170$$

Second Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} := 93$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} := 181$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} := 40 \times 60$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} := 44 \times 66.$$

Result 6.3. Let's consider following *reduced entries algebraic magic square* of order 7:

$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*(S-M)/2-A5-A6$	$A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	A11	T-S-A11
$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	A5	S-M-A5	A12	T-S-A12
A1	A2	M-A1-A2	A6	S-M-A6	A13	T-S-A13
$A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	A4	$A1+2*(S-M)-2*A4+A2-2*A5-A6$	(S-M)/2	$2*M-S$	$5*(T-S)/2-A11-A12-A13-A14$	$3*(S-T)/2+A11+A12+A13+A14$
$A1+3*(S-M)/2+A2-2*A5-A6-A4$	S-M-A4	$2*A4-S+M-A1-A2+2*A5+A6$	$2*M-S$	(S-M)/2	A14	T-S-A14
$T-3*S/2-M/2+A8+2*A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A12-A11$	A8	A9	$3*T/2-S+M/2-2*A8-2*A4+A1+A2-2*A5-A12+A11-A9-A10$	A10	(T-S)/2	$3*S-2*T$
$S/2+M/2-A8-2*A4+A1+A2-2*A5-A12+A11$	T-S-A8	T-S-A9	$2*A8+2*A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A12-A11+A9+A10-T/2-M/2$	T-S-A10	$3*S-2*T$	(T-S)/2

• Details

It is *cornered* magic square of order 7, where there are magic square of orders 3 and 5 at the upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of orders 2×3 and 2×3 are of equal width and length in each case. The magic square of order 3 is with decimal entries. To get the result without decimal entries, we must consider magic sum for order 3 as multiple of 3. The letters M, S and T are magic sums of magic squares of of orders 3, 5 and 7 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 6.4. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 7 based on the Result 6.3:

2a	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							180	2b	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							191
	4	27	29	35	15	31	39	180		3	29	31	32	16	31	49	191		
	45	20	-5	19	31	33	37	180		49	21	-7	19	29	33	47	191		
	11	13	36	21	29	35	35	180		11	13	39	21	27	35	45	191		
	27	17	31	25	10	39	31	180		28	17	27	24	15	64	16	191		
	23	33	19	10	25	37	33	180		20	31	21	15	24	37	43	191		
	60	25	27	34	29	35	-30	180		68	25	27	51	29	40	-49	191		
	10	45	43	36	41	-30	35	180		12	55	53	29	51	-49	40	191		
	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180		191	191	191	191	191	191	191	191		

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} := 60$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := 110$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} := 180$$

Second Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} := 63$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := 111$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} := 191$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} := 50 \times 75$$

$$MR_{2 \times 5} := 70 \times 175$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} := 48 \times 72$$

$$MR_{2 \times 5} := 80 \times 200.$$

Result 6.4. *Let's consider following reduced entries algebraic magic square of order 7:*

A6	2*M-A9-S+A7	S-M-A7	S-M-A6	A9	A14	T-S-A14
2*S-3*M+A9- 2*A7+A2+A1-A4	A1+A2-M/3	2*M/3-A2	2*M/3-A1	2*M-S+A4+2*A7- A2-A1-A9	A15	T-S-A15
2*A7+S-M-A6- A2-A1	4*M/3-2*A1-A2	M/3	2*A1+A2-2*M/3	A6-2*A7+A2+A1	(5/2)*T-(5/2)*S- A17-A16-A15-A14	(3/2)*S-(3/2)*T+ A14+A15+A16+A17
A4	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	S-M-A4	A16	T-S-A16
4*M-2*S-A9	A9+2*S-3*M-A7	A7	A6	S-M-A6	A17	T-S-A17
T-2*S-A7+A11+ M+A6+A15-A14	A11	A7-(1/2)*S-M- A6+(3/2)*T-A13-A12- 2*A11-A15+A14	A12	A13	(T-S)/2	3*S-2*T
A7-A11+S-M-A6- A15+A14	T-S-A11	A13+A12+2*A11- A7+M+A6+A15-A14- (1/2)*T-(1/2)*S	T-S-A12	T-S-A13	3*S-2*T	(T-S)/2

● **Details**

It is *cornered* magic square of order 7, where there is a *single-digit bordered* magic square of order 5 at the upper-left corner embedded with magic square of order 3. The two magic rectangles of orders 2×5 are of equal width and length. In order to get magic square without decimal entries, we must

consider magic sum of magic square of order 3 as multiple of 3. The letters M, S and T are magic sums of magic squares of orders 3, 5 and 7 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 6.5. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 7 based on the Result 6.4:

3a	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							150	3b	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							171
	16	58	13	14	19	24	6	150		16	57	14	15	19	24	26	171		
	-36	-7	48	49	66	25	5	150		-34	-7	48	49	65	25	25	171		
	25	86	30	-26	5	-27	57	150		26	86	30	-26	5	23	27	171		
	14	11	12	67	16	26	4	150		14	11	12	67	17	26	24	171		
	101	-28	17	16	14	27	3	150		99	-26	17	16	15	27	23	171		
	21	21	-12	22	23	15	60	150		40	21	19	22	23	25	21	171		
	9	9	42	8	7	60	15	150		10	29	31	28	27	21	25	171		
	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150		171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171		

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} := 90$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := 120$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} := 150$$

Second Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} := 90$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := 121$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} := 171$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 5} := 30 \times 50$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 5} := 30 \times 50$$

Result 6.5. Let's consider following *reduced entries algebraic magic square* of order 7:

A1	A2	S-A1-A2-A3-A4	A3	A4	A13	T-S-A13
A8-A2+A7	A5	A1+A2+A3+A4-A5-A6-A7	A6	S-A1-A3-A4-A8	A14	T-S-A14
A2+A3+A4-A5-A7	S-A1-A2-A3-A4+A6-A8	A7	A7-A2-A3+A5+A8	A1+A2+A3-A6-A7	5*(T-S)/2-A16-A15-A14-A13	3*(S-T)/2+A13+A14+A15+A16
A7-A3+A5	A1-A6+A8	A2+A3-A7	S-A1-A5-A7-A8	A7-A2+A6	A15	T-S-A15
S-A1-A4-A7-A8	A3+A4-A5	A7-A2-A3+A5+A6	A1+A2-A6	A8	A16	T-S-A16
T-S-A7+A10-A8+A14-A13	A10	A7+A8+3*(T-S)/2-A12-A11-2*A10-A14+A13	A11	A12	(T-S)/2	3*S-2*T
A7-A10+A8-A14+A13	T-S-A10	(S-T)/2+A12+A11+2*A10-A7-A8+A14-A13	T-S-A11	T-S-A12	3*S-2*T	(T-S)/2

• **Details**

It is *cornered* magic square of order 7, where there is a magic square of order 5 at the upper-left corner. The two magic rectangles of orders 2×5 are of equal width and length. Moreover, the magic square of order 5 is *pandiagonal*. The letters S and T are magic sums of magic squares of of orders 5 and 7 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 6.6. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 7 based on the Result 6.5:

4a	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							190	4b	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							175
		21	24	38	27	30	57	-7	190			21	24	39	27	30	57	-23	175
		57	33	-6	36	20	60	-10	190			57	33	-6	36	21	60	-26	175
		9	32	39	63	-3	-121	171	190			9	33	39	63	-3	-161	195	175
		45	27	12	5	51	63	-13	190			45	27	12	6	51	63	-29	175
		8	24	57	9	42	66	-16	190			9	24	57	9	42	66	-32	175
		20	48	-48	51	54	25	40	190			4	48	-72	51	54	17	73	175
		30	2	98	-1	-4	40	25	190			30	-14	106	-17	-20	73	17	175
		190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190			175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$S_{5 \times 5} := 140$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} := 190$$

Second Example

$$S_{5 \times 5} := 141$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} := 175$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 5} := 50 \times 125$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 5} := 34 \times 85$$

6.2 Self-Made Algebraic Semi-Magic Squares of Order 7

In this case, we have three result for **semi-magic** square of order 7. Conditions to bring them as magic squares are also studied.

Result 6.6. *Let's consider following reduced entries magic square of order 7:*

A15	$(7/2)*T-(9/2)*S-A8+A5-2*M-A11$	A8	$(9/2)*S-A15-A16-A10-A9-A5+2*M-(5/2)*T+A11$	A9	A10	A16
$(5/2)*T-(5/2)*S-A15+A16-A14+2*A8-A5+2*M-A13-A11$	$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*(S-M)/2-A5-A6$	$A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	$(3/2)*S-(3/2)*T+A11-2*A8+A5-2*M+A13+A14-A16+A15$
$A5-(7/2)*S-2*M+(5/2)*T-2*A8$	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	A5	S-M-A5	$(5/2)*S-(3/2)*T+2*A8-A5+2*M$
A13	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	A6	S-M-A6	T-S-A13
A14	$A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	A4	$A1+2*(S-M)-2*A4+A2-2*A5-A6$	$(S-M)/2$	$2*M-S$	T-S-A14
A11	$A1+3*(S-M)/2+A2-2*A5-A6-A4$	S-M-A4	$2*A4-S+M-A1-A2+2*A5+A6$	$2*M-S$	$(S-M)/2$	T-S-A11
$6*S-A16-4*T$	$A11+A8-A5+(7/2)*S+2*M-(5/2)*T$	T-S-A8	$A15+A16+A10+A9+(7/2)*T-(11/2)*S+A5-2*M-A11$	T-S-A9	T-S-A10	T-S-A15

• Details

It is single-digit bordered semi-magic square of order 7 embedded with a cornered magic square of order 5. It contains magic square of order 3 at upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of order 2×3

are of equal width and length. In order to get magic square without decimal entries, we must consider magic sum of magic square of order 3 as multiple of 3. Moreover, in order to get a magic square of order 7, we must have the condition $T = \frac{5}{7} \times S$. The letters M, S and T are magic sums of magic squares of orders 3, 5 and 7 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 6.7. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 7 based on the Result 6.6:

1a	semi	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							260	1b	mgc	S/5=T/7							210
	25	-204	18	276	19	20	26	180		25	-156	18	258	19	20	26	210		
	234	-7	48	49	44	6	-194	180		296	-9	52	53	50	4	-236	210		
	-241	86	30	-26	15	35	281	180		-213	94	32	-30	15	39	273	210		
	23	11	12	67	16	34	17	180		23	11	12	73	16	38	37	210		
	24	12	14	49	25	40	16	180		24	10	14	57	27	42	36	210		
	21	38	36	1	40	25	19	180		21	44	40	-3	42	27	39	210		
	94	244	22	-236	21	20	15	180		34	216	42	-198	41	40	35	210		
	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180		210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210		

The first example is **semi-magic** square and second example is a magic square. The second one is obtained by applying the condition $T = \frac{5}{7} \times S$. The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$S_{3 \times 3} := 90$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := 140$$

$$T_{Sm_{7 \times 7}} := 180$$

Second Example

$$S_{3 \times 3} := 96$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := 150$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} := 210$$

The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} := 50 \times 75$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 3} := 34 \times 81$$

Result 6.7. Let's consider following reduced entries magic square of order 7:

A18	T-S+A11+A15-A14	A11	S-A18-A19-A13-A12-2*A11-A15+A14	A12	A13	A19
5*T-6*S-A18+A19-A17-A15-A16-A14	A6	M-A6-A9-A8+A7	S-M-A7	A8	A9	5*S-4*T+A14+A15+A16+A17-A19+A18
A15	3*S-4*M-A6+A9-A5-A4	A1+A2-M/3	2*M/3-A2	2*M/3-A1	3*M-2*S+A4+A5-A9+A6	T-S-A15
A16	A5	4*M/3-2*A1-A2	M/3	2*A1+A2-2*M/3	S-M-A5	T-S-A16
A17	A4	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	S-M-A4	T-S-A17
A14	4*M-2*S-A9	A6+A9+A8+S-2*M-A7	A7	S-M-A8	S-M-A6	T-S-A14
6*S-A19-4*T	A14-A11-A15	T-S-A11	A18+A19+A13+A12+2*A11+T-2*S+A15-A14	T-S-A12	T-S-A13	T-S-A18

• **Details**

It is *single-digit bordered semi-magic square* of order 7 embedded with magic squares of orders 5 and 3. In order to get magic square without decimal entries, we must consider magic sum of magic square of order 3 as multiple of 3. Moreover, in order to get a magic square of order 7, we must have two conditions $T = \frac{5}{7} \times S$ and $S = \frac{3}{5} \times M$. The letters M, S and T are magic sums of magic squares of orders 3, 5 and 7 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 6.8. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 7 based on the Result 6.7:

2a	semi	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							250	2b	mgc	M/3=S/5=T/7							140
	38	82	31	-55	32	33	39	200		38	72	31	-105	32	33	39	140		
	-41	26	34	33	28	29	91	200		-41	26	4	13	28	29	81	140		
	35	44	13	38	39	16	15	200		35	14	23	18	19	26	5	140		
	36	25	56	30	4	35	14	200		36	25	16	20	24	15	4	140		
	37	24	21	22	47	36	13	200		37	24	21	22	17	16	3	140		
	34	31	26	27	32	34	16	200		34	11	36	27	12	14	6	140		
	61	-32	19	105	18	17	12	200		1	-32	9	145	8	7	2	140		
	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200		140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140		

The first example is **semi-magic** square and second example is a magic square. The second one is obtained by applying the conditions $T = \frac{5}{7} \times S$ and $S = \frac{3}{5} \times M$. The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example	Second Example
$S_{3 \times 3} := 90$	$S_{3 \times 3} := 60$
$S_{5 \times 5} := 150$	$S_{5 \times 5} := 100$
$T_{Sm_{7 \times 7}} := 200$	$T_{7 \times 7} := 140$

Result 6.8. Let's consider following reduced entries magic square of order 7:

A17	T-S+A10+A14-A13	A10	S-A17-A18-A12-A11-2*A10-A14+A13	A11	A12	A18
A14	A1	A2	S-A1-A2-A3-A4	A3	A4	T-S-A14
5*T-6*S-A17+A18-A16-A14-A15-A13	A8-A2+A7	A5	A1+A2+A3+A4-A5-A6-A7	A6	S-A1-A3-A4-A8	5*S-4*T+A13+A14+A15+A16-A18+A17
A15	A2+A3+A4-A5-A7	S-A1-A2-A3-A4+A6-A8	A7	A7-A2-A3+A5+A8	A1+A2+A3-A6-A7	T-S-A15
A16	A7-A3+A5	A1-A6+A8	A2+A3-A7	S-A1-A5-A7-A8	A7-A2+A6	T-S-A16
A13	S-A1-A4-A7-A8	A3+A4-A5	A7-A2-A3+A5+A6	A1+A2-A6	A8	T-S-A13
6*S-A18-4*T	A13-A10-A14	T-S-A10	A17+A18+A12+A11+2*A10+T-2*S+A14-A13	T-S-A11	T-S-A12	T-S-A17

• Details

It is **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 7, where there is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 in the middle. Moreover, in order to get a magic square of order 7, we must have the condition $T = \frac{5}{7} \times S$. The letters S and T are magic sums of magic squares of orders 5 and 7 respectively. See below two examples.

Example 6.9. Let's consider following two examples of magic squares of order 7 based on the Result 6.8:

3a	semi	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							130	3b	mgc	S/5=T/7							196
	62	94	41	-193	44	47	65	160		62	100	41	-163	44	47	65	196		
	53	14	17	36	20	23	-3	160		53	14	17	66	20	23	3	196		
	-75	50	26	-13	29	18	125	160		-75	50	26	-13	29	48	131	196		
	56	2	30	32	56	-10	-6	160		56	2	60	32	56	-10	0	196		
	59	38	20	5	3	44	-9	160		59	38	20	5	33	44	-3	196		
	50	6	17	50	2	35	0	160		50	36	17	50	2	35	6	196		
	-45	-44	9	243	6	3	-12	160		-9	-44	15	219	12	9	-6	196		
	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160		196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196		

The first example is **semi-magic** square and second example is a magic square. The second one is obtained by applying the conditions $T = \frac{5}{7} \times S$. The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$S_{5 \times 5} := 110$$

$$T_{Sm_{7 \times 7}} := 160$$

Second Example

$$S_{5 \times 5} := 140$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} := 196$$

6.3 Self-Made Algebraic Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order 7

Below are four results with examples on **reduced entries algebraic pandiagonal** magic squares of order 7.

Result 6.9. *Let's consider following reduced entries algebraic magic square of order 7:*

$A7+A22+A9+A10+A14+A1+A2+A6+A3+A5-A12-T-A16$	$A8+A23+A19-A1-A15-A6-A17+A12+A13+A4-A5$	A1	A6	$A22-A10+A19+A2-A18-A13+A3$	A15	$2^*T-A8+A16-A7-2^*A22-A9-A23-2^*A19-A14-A1-2^*A2+A18-A6+A17-2^*A3-A4$
$A19+A14+A2-A18-A17+A12+A3+2^*A4-A5-A7$	$T+A16-A7-A22-A19+A20-A14-A1-2^*A2-A11+A18-A6+A17-A3$	A2	A7	A11	$A7+A22-A19-A20+A1+A6-A12-2^*A4+A5-A16$	A19
$T-A9-A10+A23-A14-A1-A15-A6+A12-A3-A5$	$2^*A7+2^*A22+A9+A19-A20+A14+2^*A1+2^*A2+A11-A18+A15+2^*A6-A12-A13+2^*A3-A4+2^*A5-2^*T-A16$	$A14+A11+A15+A6-A4-A23-A20$	$2^*T-A8-A7-A22-A9-A23-2^*A19-A14-2^*A2-A11+A18-A6+A17-A12-A3-A4$	$A8-A7-A22+A9+A10+A23+A19+A20-A1-A11-A15-A6-A17+A12+A13+3^*A4-A5$	A16	A20
$T-A22-A23-A19-A20-A21-A2+A18+A15-A12-A4$	$A10-A23-A19+A1+A6-A12+A5$	$T+A23+A20-A14-A1-A2-A11-A15-A6-A3-A5$	$A10+A23+2^*A19+A14+2^*A2+A11-A18-A17+A12+A3+A4-T$	A12	A17	A21
$T-A7-A22+A23+A20-A14-A1-A2-A11-A15-2^*A6+A12+A13-A3+A4-A5$	$A16-A7-A22+A23+A19+A20+A21-A1-A15-A6+2^*A12+A13-A3+2^*A4-A5$	A3	A8	$T-A8+A7-A9-A23-2^*A19-A20-A14+A1-A2+A18+A15+A6+A17-2^*A12-A13-A3-3^*A4+A5$	$A7+A22+A9-A23+A19-A20-A21+2^*A14+A1+2^*A2+A11-A18+A15+2^*A6-A17-A12-A13+2^*A3+A5-T-A16$	A22
$A7+A22-A23-A20+A14+A1+A2+A11+A15+2^*A6-A12-A13+A3-2^*A4+2^*A5-T$	$A7+A22-A23-A20-A21+A14+A1+A2+A15+A6-A12-A13+A3-A4-A16$	A4	A9	A13	$2^*T+A16-2^*A7-2^*A22-A9+A23+2^*A20+A21-2^*A14-2^*A1-2^*A2-A11-2^*A15-3^*A6+2^*A12+A13-2^*A3+2^*A4-2^*A5$	A23
$A16+A20+A21-A14-A2+A17-A3$	$2^*T-A8-A7-A22-A9-A10-A19-A14-A1-A2-A6-A3-A4-A5$	A5	A10	A14	A18	$A8-A16+A7+A22+A9+A19-A20-A21+A14+A1+2^*A2-A18+A6-A17+2^*A3+A4-T$

• Details

It is an *algebraic pandiagonal* magic square of order 7 without any block. See below two examples.

Example 6.10. Let's consider following two examples representing *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 7

7x7	pan	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	7x7	pan	97	97	97	97	97	97	97
90	84	79	11	21	19	39	-163	90	90	97	77	79	11	21	19	39	-149	97
90	49	4	13	23	31	-77	47	90	90	97	49	11	13	23	31	-77	47	97
90	-20	91	7	-189	111	41	49	90	90	97	-13	77	7	-175	111	41	49	97
90	-144	-55	8	154	33	43	51	90	90	97	-137	-55	15	147	33	43	51	97
90	-4	197	15	25	-176	-20	53	90	90	97	3	197	15	25	-169	-27	53	97
90	6	-69	17	27	35	19	55	90	90	97	-1	-69	17	27	35	33	55	97
	119	-157	19	29	37	45	-2	90	90		119	-143	19	29	37	45	-9	97
	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90		97	97	97	97	97	97	97	97

The above two examples are with even and odd number magic sums. One is 90 and another is 97.

Result 6.10. Let's consider following *reduced entries algebraic* magic square of order 7:

$(2/3)*M-A1$	$A5$	$(3/2)*M+A1+A3-2*A5-3*A4$	$A5+A4-(1/3)*M+A2-A1$	$A5+2*A4-(1/6)*M-A2-A3$	$A4$	$(2/3)*M+A1-A5-A4$
$(11/6)*M-2*A5-2*A4$	$A1$	$2*A5+3*A4-(5/6)*M-A1-A3$	$M+A1-A5-A4-A2$	$(5/6)*M+A3-A5-2*A4+A2$	$A5+A4-A1$	$A5+A4-(1/2)*M$
$(1/3)*M-A1-A3+A5+A4$	$A1+A3-A5-A4+(1/3)*M$	$2*A1-(1/3)*M$	$(5/3)*M-2*A5-2*A4$	$2*A5+2*A4-(1/3)*M-2*A1$	$M-A2-A3$	$A2+A3-(1/3)*M$
$(2/3)*M+2*A1-A5-A4-A2$	$A5+A4+A2-2*A1$	$(1/3)*M-4*A1+2*A5+2*A4$	$M/3$	$(1/3)*M+4*A1-2*A5-2*A4$	$A2$	$(2/3)*M-A2$
$A3+A2-A1$	$(2/3)*M+A1-A3-A2$	$2*A1-2*A5-2*A4+M$	$2*A5+2*A4-M$	$M-2*A1$	$A3$	$(2/3)*M-A3$
$A5-(7/6)*M+2*A1+A4$	$(2/3)*M+A1-A5-A4$	$(7/6)*M-A1+A3-A5-2*A4+A2$	$(1/3)*M+A1-A2$	$A5+2*A4-(1/2)*M-A3$	$(2/3)*M-A1$	$(7/6)*M-2*A1$
$A5+A4-A1$	$(2/3)*M-2*A1+A4$	$A1-A3-(1/2)*M+A5+2*A4-A2$	$(1/3)*M-A1+A2$	$(7/6)*M+A3-A5-2*A4$	$2*A1-2*A4+(2/3)*M-A5$	$A1$

• Details

It is an *algebraic pandiagonal double-digit bordered* magic square of order 7. See below two examples. The inner block is a magic square of order 3. To avoid *decimal* or *factional* numbers entries, the magic sum of order 3 should be multiple of 3. The letter M represents the magic sum of order 3, and $T = \frac{7}{3} \times M$, is the magic sum of order 7. See below two examples.

Example 6.11. Let's consider following two examples representing *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 7

7x7	pan	98	98	98	98	98	98	98	7x7	pan	112	112	112	112	112	112	112
98	17	23	-15	32	25	20	-4	98	112	21	23	-6	30	24	20	0	112
98	-9	11	43	-4	3	32	22	98	112	2	11	38	2	8	32	19	112
98	29	-1	8	-16	50	11	17	98	112	31	1	6	-6	48	17	15	112
98	-7	35	56	14	-28	14	14	98	112	-3	35	58	16	-26	14	18	112
98	20	8	-22	44	20	17	11	98	112	20	12	-16	38	26	17	15	112
98	16	-4	6	11	25	17	27	98	112	9	0	13	13	22	21	34	112
	32	26	22	17	3	-13	11	98		32	30	19	19	10	-9	11	112
	98	98	98	98	98	98	98	98		112	112	112	112	112	112	112	112

According to Result 6.10, the magic sums are $T_{17 \times 7} := \frac{7}{3} \times 42 = 98$ and $T_{27 \times 7} := \frac{7}{3} \times 48 = 112$, where 42 and 48 are magic sums of order 3 respectively.

Result 6.11. Let's consider following reduced entries algebraic magic square of order 7:

A1	A2	S-A1-A2-A3-A4	A3	A4	A8	(2/5)*S-A8
S-A10-A4-A8-A2	A5	A1+A2+A3+A4-A5-A6-(1/5)*S	A6	(1/5)*S+A10-A1+A8-A3	(2/5)*S-A9	A9
A2+A3+A4-A5-(1/5)*S	A10+A6-A1-A2+A8+(1/5)*S-A3	(1/5)*S	A5+S-A10-A4-A8-A2-A3	A1+A2+A3-A6-(1/5)*S	(3/5)*S-A10-A8	A8+A10-(1/5)*S
(1/5)*S-A3+A5	(4/5)*S+A1-A10-A4-A8-A6	A2+A3-(1/5)*S	A10+A4+A8-A5-A1	(1/5)*S-A2+A6	A9	(2/5)*S-A9
A10+A8-A1	A3+A4-A5	(1/5)*S-A2-A3+A5+A6	A1+A2-A6	(4/5)*S-A10-A4-A8	A10	(2/5)*S-A10
(1/5)*S+A1-A8	A1+(2/5)*S-A10+A9-A4-A8	(3/5)*S-A4-A1	A10+A4+A8-A9-A1	A4+A8-(1/5)*S	(1/5)*S	(1/5)*S
(1/5)*S-A1+A8	A10+A4+A8-A9-A1	A4+A1-(1/5)*S	A1+(2/5)*S-A10+A9-A4-A8	(3/5)*S-A4-A8	(1/5)*S	(1/5)*S

• **Details**

It is an algebraic pandiagonal cornered magic square of order 7 with pandiagonal magic square of order 5 at upper-left corner. The letter S represents the magic sum of order 5, and $T = \frac{7}{5} \times S$, is

the magic sum of order 7. To avoid *decimal* or *factional* numbers entries, the magic sum of order 5 should be multiple of 5. In this case, both the magic squares of orders 5 and 7 are *pndiagonal*. See below two examples.

Example 6.12. Let's consider following two examples representing *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 7

7x7	pan	56	56	56	56	56	56	56	7x7	pan	63	63	63	63	63	63	63
56	11	14	-22	17	20	32	-16	56	63	11	14	-17	17	20	32	-14	63
56	-64	23	5	26	50	-19	35	56	63	-59	23	4	26	51	-17	35	63
56	20	62	8	-58	8	-46	62	56	63	19	63	9	-53	7	-43	61	63
56	14	-73	23	56	20	35	-19	56	63	15	-69	22	56	21	35	-17	63
56	59	14	26	-1	-58	38	-22	56	63	59	14	27	-1	-54	38	-20	63
56	-13	-28	-7	44	44	8	8	56	63	-12	-26	-4	44	43	9	9	63
	29	44	23	-28	-28	8	8	56		30	44	22	-26	-25	9	9	63
	56	56	56	56	56	56	56	56		63	63	63	63	63	63	63	63

According to Result 6.11, the magic sums are $T1_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7}{5} \times 40 = 56$ and $T2_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7}{5} \times 45 = 63$, where 40 and 45 are the magic sums of order 5 respectively.

Result 6.12. Let's consider following *reduced entries algebraic* magic square of order 7:

S/5	$3*S/5-A8-A1$	$2*S/5-A7$	$3*A1+3*A8-A9-2*A7$	A7	$A9+2*A7-2*A1-2*A8$	S/5
A8	A1	A2	$4*S/5-3*A1-A2-A3+A9+2*A7-3*A8$	A3	$S/5-A9-2*A7+2*A1+3*A8$	$2*S/5-A8$
$2*S/5-A9$	$A9+S/5+A7-A1-A2$	A4	$3*A1+A2+A3-A9-2*A7+3*A8-A4-A5$	A5	$4*S/5-2*A1-A3+A7-3*A8$	A9
$2*S/5+A7-A1-3*A8$	$A2+A3-A9-2*A7+2*A1+3*A8-A4$	$4*S/5-2*A1-A2-A3+A7-3*A8+A5$	$(1/5)*S$	$A9+S/5+A7-A1-A2-A3+A4$	$A1+A2+A3-A5-S/5$	$A1+3*A8-A7$
A9	$S/5-A3+A4$	$A9+A7-A5$	$A2+A3-S/5$	$4*S/5-A4-A9-A7$	$S/5-A2+A5$	$2*S/5-A9$
$S/5-A7+A1+2*A8$	$3*S/5+A7-2*A1-3*A8$	$A3+S/5-A9-2*A7+2*A1+3*A8-A4$	$S/5-A2-A3+A4+A5$	$A1+A2-A5$	$A9+A7-A1$	$S/5+A7-A1-2*A8$
S/5	$A8+A1-S/5$	A7	$2*S/5+A9+2*A7-3*A1-3*A8$	$2*S/5-A7$	$2*S/5-A9-2*A7+2*A1+2*A8$	S/5

• Details

It is an *algebraic pandiagonal single-digit bordered magic square of order 7*, where *pandiagonal magic square of order 5* in the inner part. The letter S represents the magic sum of order 5, and $T = \frac{7}{5} \times S$, is the magic sum of order 7. To avoid *decimal* or *factional* numbers entries, the magic sum of order 5 should be multiple of 5. In this case, both the magic squares of orders 5 and 7 are *pndiagonal*. See below two examples.

Example 6.13. Let's consider following two examples representing *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 7

7x7	pan	49	49	49	49	49	49	49	7x7	pan	70	70	70	70	70	70	70
49	7	-8	-3	34	17	-5	7	49	70	10	1	3	18	17	11	10	70
49	18	11	12	-31	13	30	-4	49	70	18	11	12	-3	13	17	2	70
49	-5	20	14	30	15	-44	19	49	70	-15	39	14	14	15	-32	35	70
49	-34	34	-41	7	21	14	48	49	70	-28	18	-29	10	40	11	48	70
49	19	8	21	18	-22	10	-5	49	70	35	11	37	15	-26	13	-15	70
49	37	-38	29	11	8	25	-23	49	70	40	-29	16	14	8	41	-20	70
	7	22	17	-20	-3	19	7	49		10	19	17	2	3	9	10	70
	49	49	49	49	49	49	49	49		70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70

According to Result 6.12, the magic sums are $T1_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7}{5} \times 35 = 49$ and $T2_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7}{5} \times 50 = 70$, where 35 and 50 are the magic sums of order 5 respectively.

Result 6.13. Let's consider following *reduced entries algebraic* magic square of order 7:

$A1$	$(6/5)*S+A9-2*M$	$3*M-(6/5)*S-A9-A1$	$A6$	$S-M-A6$	$A13$	$(2/5)*S-A13$
$2*M-(4/5)*S-A9$	$M-A1-(1/5)*S$	$A1+S+A9-2*M$	$A7$	$S-M-A7$	$(1/5)*S-A7-A16-A1+M$	$(1/5)*S+A7+A16+A1-M$
$(4/5)*S+A9-M-A1$	$A1+2*M-S-A9$	$(1/5)*S$	$S-A7-A1-A6-A9$	$A7+A1+A6-M+A9$	$(9/5)*S-A1-A6-2*M$	$A1+A6+2*M-(7/5)*S$
$(11/5)*S-3*M-A6$	$S-M-A7$	$A7-A1+A6+A9-(1/5)*S$	$A1$	$4*M-A9-2*S$	$A16$	$(2/5)*S-A16$
$2*M+A6-(6/5)*S$	$A7$	$A1-A6-M-A9+(6/5)*S-A7$	$A9$	$S-A1-M$	$A7+2*A1+A6+M-S-A13$	$A13+(7/5)*S-A7-2*A1-A6-M$
$M+2*A1-A13-(3/5)*S$	$2*M-(7/5)*S+A7+A16$	$A6+M-(2/5)*S-A1$	$(3/5)*S-A16-A1$	$(14/5)*S-A6-4*M-A7+A13$	$(1/5)*S$	$(1/5)*S$
$S-M-2*A1+A13$	$(9/5)*S-A7-A16-2*M$	$A1-A6-M+(4/5)*S$	$A16+A1-(1/5)*S$	$4*M-A13-(12/5)*S+A6+A7$	$(1/5)*S$	$(1/5)*S$

• Details

It is an *algebraic pandiagonal cornered* magic square of order 7, where a magic square of order 5 in the upper-left corner. It again have a *semi-magic* square of order 3 at the upper-left corner. The letter M, S, T represents the magic sum of orders 3, 5 and 7, where $T = \frac{7}{5} \times S$ represents the magic square of order 7 To avoid *decimal* or *factional* numbers entries, the magic sum of order 5 should be multiple of 5. In this case, only the magic square of order 7 is *pandiagonal*, while the orders 3 and 5 are *semi-magic* and *magic* sums respectively. See below two examples.

Example 6.14. Let's consider following two examples representing *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 7

7x7	pan	105	105	105	105	105	105	105	7x7	pan	112	112	112	112	112	112	112
105	11	50	-34	12	36	15	15	105	112	11	50	-31	12	38	15	17	112
105	-20	1	46	13	35	2	28	105	112	-18	3	45	13	37	6	26	112
105	36	-24	15	25	23	58	-28	105	112	37	-23	16	30	20	61	-29	112
105	72	35	13	11	-56	16	14	105	112	74	37	12	11	-54	16	16	112
105	-24	13	35	14	37	-16	46	105	112	-24	13	38	14	39	-18	50	112
105	-11	-22	-2	18	92	15	15	105	112	-11	-23	-1	21	94	16	16	112
	41	52	32	12	-62	15	15	105		43	55	33	11	-62	16	16	112
	105	105	105	105	105	105	105	105		112	112	112	112	112	112	112	112

Thus, the magic sums for the orders 7, 5 and 3 of first example are 105, 75 and 27 and for the second example are 112, 80 and 30 respectively. For the order 3 these values are *semi-magic*

Result 6.14. Let's consider following *reduced entries algebraic magic square* of order 7:

M-A2-A3	A1-A2+M/3	M/3	A2+A3-A1	A2	A4	(2/3)*M-A4
2*A2+A3-A1-(1/3)*M	A2+A3-(1/3)*M	(2/3)*M-A3	2*M/3-A2	A1-2*A2+M-A3	A5	(2/3)*M-A5
M/3	(4/3)*M-2*A2-A3	M/3	2*A2+A3-(2/3)*M	M/3	2*A2+A3-(2/3)*M	(4/3)*M-2*A2-A3
A1	A2	A3	M-A2-A3	2*M/3-A1	(2/3)*M-A5	A5
2*M/3-A2	M/3+A2-A1	M/3	(2/3)*M-A2-A3+A1	A2+A3-(1/3)*M	(5/3)*M-A4-2*A2-A3	A4+2*A2+A3-M
(4/3)*M-A4-A2-A3	(2/3)*M-A5	A3	A5	A4+A2-(1/3)*M	(1/3)*M	(1/3)*M
A4+A2+A3-(2/3)*M	A5	(2/3)*M-A3	(2/3)*M-A5	M-A2-A4	(1/3)*M	(1/3)*M

• **Details**

It is an *algebraic pandiagonal cornered magic square* of order 7, where a *pandiagonal magic square* of order 5 is in the *upper-leftcorner*, and It is an *algebraic single-digit bordered magic*

square with magic square of order 3 in the middle. The letter M, S and T represents the magic sum of orders 3, 5 and 7, where $T = \frac{7}{3} \times M$ and $S = \frac{5}{3} \times M$. To avoid **decimal** or **factional** entries, the magic sum of order 3 should be multiple of 3. In this case, both the magic squares of orders 5 and 7 are **pandiagonal**, while the order 3 is a magic square. See below two examples.

Example 6.15. Let's consider following two examples representing **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 7

7x7	pan	63	63	63	63	63	63	63	7x7	pan	77	77	77	77	77	77	77
63	-8	6	9	22	16	22	-4	63	77	-2	8	11	22	16	22	0	77
63	29	26	-1	2	-11	25	-7	63	77	27	24	3	6	-5	25	-3	77
63	9	-15	9	33	9	33	-15	63	77	11	-7	11	29	11	29	-7	77
63	13	16	19	-8	5	-7	25	63	77	13	16	19	-2	9	-3	25	77
63	2	12	9	-4	26	-28	46	63	77	6	14	11	0	24	-18	40	77
63	-21	-7	19	25	29	9	9	63	77	-13	-3	19	25	27	11	11	77
	39	25	-1	-7	-11	9	9	63		35	25	3	-3	-5	11	11	77
	63	63	63	63	63	63	63	63		77	77	77	77	77	77	77	77

Thus, the magic sums for the orders 7, 5 and 3 of first example are 63, 45 and 27 and for the second example are 77, 55 and 33 respectively.

Result 6.15. Let's consider following **reduced entries algebraic** magic square of order 7:

$(1/3)*M$	M	$(2/3)*M - A2$	$-(1/3)*M$	A2	$(1/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M$
$-(1/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M$	A1	$2*M/3 - A1$	M	$2*M/3 - M$	M
A2	$(2/3)*M - A1$	M/3	A1	M/3	M/3	$(2/3)*M - A2$
M	A1	$(2/3)*M - A1$	$(1/3)*M$	$(-A1)$	$(2/3)*M + A1$	$-(1/3)*M$
$(2/3)*M - A2$	$-(1/3)*M$	M/3	$M + A1 - M/3$	$(1/3)*M$	$(2/3)*M - A1$	A2
$(1/3)*M$	M	M/3	$(-A1)$	A1	$(1/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M$
$(1/3)*M$	$-(1/3)*M$	A2	M	$(2/3)*M - A2$	$(1/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M$

• **Details**

It is an *algebraic single-digit pandiagonal* magic square of order 7 embedded with a *cornered pandiagonal* magic square of order 5. It contains a magic squares of order 3 at the upper left corner. The letters M, S and T represents magic squares of orders 3, 5 and 7 respectively. The magic squares of orders 5 and 7 are *pandiagonal*. The magic sums are $T = (7/3) * M$ and $S = (5/3) * M$, where M is the magic sum of order 3. To avoid *decimal* entries, the magic sum of order 3 should be multiple of 3. See below two examples:

Example 6.16. Let's consider following two examples representing *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 7

7x7	pan								42	7x7	pan								49
42	6	18	-2	-6	14	6	6	42	49	7	21	0	-7	14	7	7	49		
42	-6	6	11	1	18	-6	18	42	49	-7	7	11	3	21	-7	21	49		
42	14	1	6	11	6	6	-2	42	49	14	3	7	11	7	7	0	49		
42	18	11	1	6	-11	23	-6	42	49	21	11	3	7	-11	25	-7	49		
42	-2	-6	6	23	6	1	14	42	49	0	-7	7	25	7	3	14	49		
42	6	18	6	-11	11	6	6	42	49	7	21	7	-11	11	7	7	49		
	6	-6	14	18	-2	6	6	42		7	-7	14	21	0	7	7	49		
	42	42	42	42	42	42	42	42		49	49	49	49	49	49	49	49		

Thus, the magic sums for the orders 7, 5 and 3 of the first example are 42, 30 and 18 and for the second example are 49, 35 and 21 respectively.

Result 6.16. Let's consider following *reduced entries algebraic* magic square of order 7:

$(1/3)*M$	$(2/3)*M-A3$	$A2+(1/3)*M-3*A3$	$A2$	$3*A3+(1/3)*M-A2$	$M/3+A3-A2$	$(1/3)*M$
$A3$	$M/3$	$A1-A2+M/3$	$M/3$	$M-A1-M/3$	$A2$	$(2/3)*M-A3$
$3*A3+(1/3)*M-A2$	$(1/3)*M+A2-A1$	$2*M/3-M/3$	$M/3+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$A1-A2+M/3$	$A2+(1/3)*M-3*A3$
$(2/3)*M-A2$	$M/3$	$(2/3)*M-A2$	$M/3$	$A2$	$M/3$	$A2$
$A2+(1/3)*M-3*A3$	$A1$	$A2$	$M-M/3-A2$	$M/3$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*A3+(1/3)*M-A2$
$(1/3)*M-A3+A2$	$2*M/3-A2$	$M/3+A2-A1$	$M/3$	$M/3+A1-M/3$	$(1/3)*M$	$A3+M/3-A2$
$(1/3)*M$	$A3$	$3*A3+(1/3)*M-A2$	$(2/3)*M-A2$	$A2+(1/3)*M-3*A3$	$(1/3)*M-A3+A2$	$(1/3)*M$

• **Details**

It is an *algebraic single-digit pandiagonal* magic square of order 7 having magic square of order 3 in the inner part. The letters M, S and T represents magic squares of orders 3, 5 and 7 respectively. The magic squares of orders 5 and 7 are *pandiagonal*. The magic sums are $T = (7/3) * M$ and $S = (5/3) * M$, where M is the magic sum of order 3. To avoid *decimal* entries, the magic sum of order 3 should be multiple of 3. See below two examples:

Example 6.17. Let's consider following two examples representing *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 7

7x7	pan							56	7x7	pan							63
56	8	-1	-28	15	44	10	8	56	63	9	1	-27	15	45	11	9	63
56	17	8	3	8	6	15	-1	56	63	17	9	4	9	8	15	1	63
56	44	13	8	15	1	3	-28	56	63	45	14	9	15	3	4	-27	63
56	1	8	1	8	15	8	15	56	63	3	9	3	9	15	9	15	63
56	-28	10	15	1	8	6	44	56	63	-27	10	15	3	9	8	45	63
56	6	1	13	8	10	8	10	56	63	7	3	14	9	10	9	11	63
	8	17	44	1	-28	6	8	56		9	17	45	3	-27	7	9	63
	56	56	56	56	56	56	56	56		63	63	63	63	63	63	63	63

Thus, the magic sums for the orders 7, 5 and 3 of the first example are 56, 40 and 24 and for the second example are 63, 45 and 27 respectively.

7 Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation Numbers

For author's contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation numbers** please see the links below:

- **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares,
 - (i) <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=668>
 - (ii) <https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>
- **Inder J. Taneja**, Recreation of Numbers,
 - (i) <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=671>
 - (ii) <https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>

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